

ACINO

Application-Centric IP/optical
Network Orchestration

ACINO / D2.2

Final report on use cases and application requirements, and preliminary techno-economic evaluation of ACINO concepts

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	3
2 Application characterization	5
2.1 Service categorisation	5
2.2 Applications description and characterization	6
2.2.1 Apps related to Broadband services and cloud services	6
2.2.2 Apps related to Machine-based services	8
2.2.3 Apps related to advanced new services emerging from 5G	11
2.3 Summary of the application characterization	13
3 Overview of the ACINO architecture and the application aware multi-layer operations	16
3.1 ACINO orchestrator overview	16
3.2 Multi-layer Connections Configuration	18
3.2.1 Provisioning	18
3.2.2 Explicit Route Provisioning	18
3.2.3 Route Restricted Provisioning	18
3.2.4 Service Resilience Provisioning	18
3.2.5 Bandwidth Provisioning	19
3.2.6 Traffic Engineering Re-Routing	19
3.3 Multi-layer failure handling	19
3.4 Multi-layer Shared Backup Router	20
4 Use cases	22
4.1 Application-based Datacentre Interconnection	22
4.2 Enabling dynamic 5G services	24
4.3 Application-specific protection strategies	27
4.4 Secure Transmission as a Service	28
4.5 Dynamic Virtual CDN deployment	31
4.6 Application-centric in-operation network planning	32

5 Reference Network	35
5.1 Reference network model and definitions	35
5.1.1 IP network architecture	35
5.1.2 Metro architecture	36
5.1.3 Access network	36
5.2 Spanish Reference Network	37
5.2.1 Network evolution KPIs	37
5.2.2 Mobile Backhaul/Metro scenario	39
5.2.3 IP layer	43
5.2.4 Optical layer infrastructure	45
6 Network cost model and preliminary evaluations	47
6.1 ACINO cost model description	47
6.1.1 Previous models and related data	47
6.1.2 Cost model comparison and validation	51
6.1.3 ACINO cost model for IP layer	55
6.1.4 ACINO cost model for Optical layer	56
6.2 Cost module Implementation in ACINO resource allocation framework	57
6.2.1 Overview of ACINO framework and implementation remarks	57
6.2.2 Cost module implementation details	57
6.3 Preliminary results	58
6.3.1 Cost comparison methodology	59
6.3.2 Assumed application driven resource allocation scenario and characteristics	60
6.3.3 Cost evaluation results and discussion	61
6.3.4 Main conclusion and remarks	64

List of figures

Figure 3.1: Simplified schema of the ACINO orchestrator.	17
Figure 3.2: Multi-layer IP-port resilient mechanism.	20
Figure 3.3: Resilience schemes in a hierarchical topology.	21
Figure 4.1: Application centric Intent-based IP optical orchestration.	23
Figure 4.2: Illustration of a UDN deployment at a stadium (from [METD65]).	24
Figure 4.3: Illustration of traffic separation based on application in the access node located at the UDN deployment site.	26
Figure 4.4: Savings due to multi-layer strategies.	27
Figure 4.5: Solutions to deal with a failure in a multi-layer scenario.	28
Figure 4.6: Percent of respondents reporting cyber attacks ¹ based on a survey of more than 500 executives of US businesses, law enforcement services, and government agencies (Multiple answers allowed per question).	29
Figure 4.7: Datacenter interconnect market forecast (Ovum DCI Market Forecast Nov'14).	30
Figure 4.8: vCDN case study.	32
Figure 4.9: Evolution towards in-operations planning.	33
Figure 4.10: Application oriented planning process.	33
Figure 5.1: Network reference model.	35
Figure 5.2: Thousands of broadband (xDSL and FTTH) users of Telefonica in Spain.	37
Figure 5.3: Thousands of FTTH users of Telefonica in Spain.	37
Figure 5.4: Thousands of Pay TV users of Telefonica in Spain.	38
Figure 5.5: Example of metro ring topology with no optical layer.	39
Figure 5.6: Physical topology for dark fiber deployments.	39
Figure 5.7: Physical and logical topology for coloured ring deployments.	40
Figure 5.8: Example of CWDM/DWDM metro architecture with optical nodes.	40
Figure 5.9: Example of passive optical metro architecture.	41
Figure 5.10: Metro network with OTN layer.	42
Figure 5.11: Reference network scenario.	42
Figure 5.12: Lower metro ring topology.	43
Figure 5.13: Access and transit router interconnection.	43
Figure 5.14: Transit routers topology and location of interconnection routers.	44
Figure 5.15: Telefónica reference network. Regional domains.	45
Figure 5.16: Telefónica reference network. National domain.	45
Figure 6.1: Network scenario of the study.	52
Figure 6.2: Node model.	52

Figure 6.3: Cost model comparison.....	53
Figure 6.4: Cost model comparison when all curves star at the same point.	53
Figure 6.5: Cost model linear approximations.	54
Figure 6.6: Cost report as seen in Net2Plan(left) and in browser (right).	58
Figure 6.7: Evaluation options for the application and non-application aware cases.	59
Figure 6.8: Total network cost and IP link variations over the simulation time.....	62
Figure 6.9: Overall network cost for different load values.....	62

List of tables

Table 2-1: Summary of the application characterization.	14
Table 4-1: Predicted aggregated traffic volumes for the stadium scenario and an office UDN deployment [NGM5G].....	26
Table 4-2: Constraints for of optically-restored capacity.....	28
Table 4-3: Comparison of different encryption mechanisms.....	30
Table 5-1: Access profile in Spain.	37
Table 5-2: Number of channels for basic and premium Movistar+ customers.....	38
Table 5-3: Regions, and number of aggregation routers.	44
Table 6-1: Metro Ethernet costs – ICT FP7 STRONGEST cost model [RAM13].....	47
Table 6-2: OTN costs – ICT FP7 STRONGEST cost model [RAM13].....	48
Table 6-3: IP costs – ICT FP7 FOX-C cost model [THO15].	49
Table 6-4: OTN costs – ICT FP7 FOX-C cost model [THO15].	49
Table 6-5: Metro Ethernet costs – CISCO.	50
Table 6-6: OTN costs – CISCO.	50
Table 6-7: Slope and interception values.	54
Table 6-8: IP cost values used.....	55
Table 6-9: OTN cost values used.	56
Table 6-10: Performance values for different cases.....	61
Table 6-11: Cost difference of ACINO (A2) with respect to other cases.	63
Table 6-12: Performance characteristics and cost difference of the reference ACINO case and ACINO case applied over network with limited optical resources per link (i.e. resulting in high blocking probability.....	64

Executive Summary

Applications are currently aggregated in the network infrastructure and receive common treatment in the different network segments even for critical parameters like bandwidth, latency, restoration or resilience. Indeed, the IP layer provides a transport to multiple applications by aggregating their traffic onto optical connections. However, this mapping is done on the basis of the destination address, and this is coarse by nature, as the traffic is not treated according to the requirements of the application that generates it. The ACINO concept is built on the premise that by applying multi-layer resource optimization algorithms with an application-centric approach, applications can receive a network service tailored to their requirements, while the network resources can be appropriately allocated. The value of a more direct mapping of application flows onto the network services can be significant, because it allows that the specific requirements of the application layer directly mapped onto the packet or the optical layer.

To evaluate this application-centric approach, it is necessary to have a characterization of the most relevant applications today as well as the emerging applications in the future that make valuable use of such application centric multi-layer IP-optical networks. Therefore the most dominant and demanding (in terms of service requirements) application are identified and categorized according to: a) Broadband services and cloud services, which include the current OTT, broadband access, social media and cloud services, b) Machine-based services, which include all the emerging machine-type communications related to the operation and content update of data centres as well as the IoT monitoring services, c) Advanced new services, including primarily the emerging 5G services that are envisioned today. The services are characterized in terms of: bandwidth requirements, usage and location, latency requirements, availability (or equally protection) requirements and security requirements.

The network architecture, where the applications will be transported, is based on packet/optical networks. The packet equipment is deployed end to end in the network and optical networks are being deployed closer to the end-user to increase the network capacity. This reference architecture has also been used to identify the multi-layer network operations that the ACINO orchestrator must perform in order to configure and adapt the resources to the application requirements.

Once we have clarified the applications and the network operations, the ACINO consortium has selected some applications and relevant network operations to illustrate, with specific use cases, the value proposition of application centric IP/optical networks. There are five case studies explain in detail in this document: (1) application-based data center interconnection, (2) enabling dynamic 5G services, (3) application-specific protection strategies, (4) secure transmission as a service, (5) dynamic virtual CDN deployment and (6) application-centric in-operation network planning. The case studies are representative examples to demonstrate the value added by the ACINO concept, since they consider not only the network but also the application layer.

This deliverable also includes an overview of the reference network architecture that will be used in the planning and techno-economic studies of the project. The multi-layer network architecture is defined based on the information available for the IP and optical layer infrastructure of the Spanish national network. A reference network is extracted and describes the national backbone and regional networks. This is

accompanied by the related traffic load data and predictions for future load increase. The reference network is important in ACINO for the network performance evaluation studies of the ACINO resource allocation frameworks as well as the cost evaluation studies that will follow in the upcoming deliverables of WP2.

A network cost model is extracted by combining data from the FP7 ICT-STRONGEST project, FP7 ICT-FOX-C project and the open list price of IP and Optical equipment by Cisco. Based on cost model comparisons and studies it is concluded that the final cost model will follow the FOX-C model which will be updated with the latest technology solutions available. In order to evaluate the cost of the network, a cost evaluation module was developed in Net2Plan and is connected with the ACINO resource allocation and optimization framework developed in WP3. It is designed to be linked with excel spreadsheet in order to allow a simple and fast update of the cost data if needed. A detailed reporting function is also included for extracting cost statistics. Preliminary cost evaluation studies have been carried out considering two application classes, one with strict latency and availability requirements and a best effort class. The results show that the added cost required for the ACINO case in order to provide application awareness is less than 5% compared to a multi-layer resource optimization case without application aware features. In addition the optimization function achieves a cost benefit in the use of network resources around 16% compared to a non-optimized solution.

1 Introduction

The Internet has evolved over time into a three-tier infrastructure: the top tier constitutes of applications driving the traffic and ultimately the requirements of the lower layers. These applications could be consumer applications such as video, audio, gaming, file-sharing, communication, social networking, consumer cloud access etc. [SAN13], or business applications such as backup or inter-site connectivity or various datacenter-to-datacenter (DC2DC) interactions, such as distributed search or VM migration. The application's traffic usually passes through a grooming layer, typically IP/MPLS, which aggregates multiple small flows into larger "pipes" that can be mapped effectively onto connections in the underlying optical layer. Additional grooming of IP traffic can also be performed on OTN before offloading traffic onto optical networks. Traffic grooming is effective in maximizing capacity utilization and reducing management complexity. However, mapping a large number of small flows, belonging to different applications, into a small number of very large and static lightpaths means that specific application requirements, such as latency or protection constraints, are seldom guaranteed after the grooming process. While some of the requirements may be satisfied implicitly by the configuration of the infrastructure, application agnostic grooming is an obstacle to effective service fulfilment.

The ACINO (Application Centric IP/Optical Networks Orchestration) project promotes a novel application-centric network concept, which differentiates the service offered to each application all the way down to the optical layer, thereby overcoming the disconnect that the grooming layer introduces between service requirements and their fulfilment in the optical layer. This allows catering to the needs of emerging medium-large applications, such as database migration in datacenters.

To realize this vision, ACINO proposes the architecture for an orchestrator, which exposes the capability for applications to define service requirements using a set of high level primitives and intents, and then performs multi-layer (IP and optical) planning and optimization to map these onto a multi-layer service on the network infrastructure. The orchestrator also targets the re-optimization of the allocated resources, by means of an application-aware in-operation planning module.

Finally, the evaluation of the cost benefits with the use of ACINO approach is essential in order to promote the applicability of the overall concept. For this reason a valid and updated cost model is required in order to accurately predict the overall network cost by considering the cost of the network elements and resources. This cost model must be combined with the resource allocation and optimization procedures proposed by ACINO, building a cost evaluation model that is next used to translate the optimised use of resources into cost saving predictions.

The rest of the document is organized into five sections. Section 2 presents an initial taxonomy of the applications that are supported by ACINO solutions and extracts their key characteristics and service requirement types that can be addressed by the ACINO approach. Section 3 provides an overview of the ACINO orchestrator architecture and a detailed explanation of the network operations in multi-layer environments. Next in section 4, the updated and final versions of the use cases of this project are presented and described, highlighting in each case the added-value of the ACINO approach. Details about the reference network and the different network segments are presented in section 5. Finally, section 6 contains the

description of the adopted cost model and the description of the implemented network cost evaluation module that contains the cost model. Preliminary results are presented at the end of section 6 commenting on the achieved cost benefits.

REMARK:

This deliverable presents the updated and final findings of the work performed within task T2.1. The initial studies, findings and definitions have been presented in deliverable D2.1. Most of these outcomes are also repeated in this document since this version is open to public. In addition to D2.1, this document presents a new section on the application characterization with emphasis on demanding future applications that are expected to define the service requirement of the supported classes. Moreover, this deliverable contains a new section on the the adopted cost model, the implementation of the cost evaluation module and preliminary techno-economic results. Finally, the sections on the use cases and the reference network have been updated.

2 Application characterization

Networks are evolving towards unified multi-domain data provisioning infrastructures supporting a huge variety of services that rely on personal, machine driven and machine-to-machine type of applications. The role of emerging networking solutions such as 5G and cloud-based networking is vital both for the evolution of the traditional core business services, as well as for the determination of the new advanced services that can be offered in the future. On one hand the current applications are expected to be enhanced, both in terms of content (richer media, HD imaging etc.) and volume (larger connected society, mobile availability), thus posing huge data growth in data traffic. On the other hand, new applications and capabilities are expected to arise from the full adoption of the 5G and cloud based networking.

In this chapter we categorize and characterize the most important applications that are foreseen in the near future. The final goal is to classify the applications according to key requirements (bandwidth, latency, availability security etc.) and then consider these attributes in the optimized resource allocation functions of the ACINO controller, thus adding application awareness in the routing and allocation processes.

2.1 Service categorisation

For operators and specifically infrastructure owners the supported applications (current, planned and future ones) can be categorized under three main service provisioning areas:

a. Broadband services and cloud services

- This category includes all voice and internet access services that are currently the main revenue source for operators. This, as of today, includes mobile broadband services for which users are expecting fast broadband connectivity (similar to fixed access) and good availability. The majority of applications rely on over-the-top (OTT) applications and in some cases cloud-based services. Advancements in this area are expected with respect to the connectivity data rates and the availability of on demand services (typically through OTT application solutions). However guaranteed content delivery services may also be deployed by operators to overcome the security and bandwidth limitations of OTT services in particular with the increase of mobile users.

b. Machine-based services

- This category includes all services related to emerging machine-type communications. These can be further divided into IoT services (related with monitoring of collected data, processing of collected information and dissemination of critical information to public) and services related with the operation of data centres.

c. Advanced new services

- This category includes advanced 5G services that are envisioned with the introduction of the next generation integrated wireless-fixed networks, offering high bandwidth, low latency and increased security and availability features. The services are described for different

vertical sectors that include: media and entertainment, automotive, health, smart factory and energy. The key focus in ACINO is on services related with the first three verticals as applications in these verticals have more demanding service requirements.

2.2 Applications description and characterization

According to the aforementioned categorization, the most advanced and demanding applications are presented and characterized below.

2.2.1 Apps related to Broadband services and cloud services

OTT video services

Description: For this service, the network operator and the OTT video provider are separate entities. The video customer uses the network to retrieve the content from an OTT video provider (Google, Facebook, Netflix, etc.). A unicast video stream is sent from the video provider to the terminal of the customer through the network of the network operator. The terminal can be any device that can visualize video content (laptop, smart TV, smart phone, tablet, etc.). The network usually transports this traffic as a best-effort service. Interactive video services like video conferencing and live meetings are also typically treated as OTT by network operators.

Requirements: Bandwidth: depends on quality profile (SD or HD), Latency: Not applicable, QoS: Best Effort, Encryption: HTTPS, Flow nature: Unicast.

Video Content Delivery Network

Description: For this service, it is assumed that the network operator owns the video platform. The operator can use a Content Delivery Network (CDN) to distribute the video content. There are some injection points in the network that can deliver videos for the unicast services (Video on Demand and Time Shift). The Video on Demand (VoD) is a video content (Movie, TV Show) that the operator can transmit to the user. It is distributed through a unicast flow which is sent to the set-top box (STB). A Time Shift (TS) video is a unicast flow from the CDN to either watch a recorded movie or a Live TV channel, which is delayed [RAV].

Requirements: Latency =10ms -150ms RTT [LDVM], Bandwidth = 10-100 Gbps

Broadcasting (Live TV)

Description: For this service, it is assumed that the network operator owns the video platform. This allows the operator to offer services like Live TV. Live TV is typically a multicast stream that is served to the DSLAMs or OLTs. The STB of the end user subscribes to a multicast stream, depending on the selected channel.

Requirements: Bandwidth: Depends on quality profile (HD to 4k), Latency: 200ms, QoS: High Priority, Encryption: Not Required, Flow nature: Multicast

Cloud gaming

Description: While serious games gaming was once confined to expensive high-end PCs or consoles attached to the living room's television, more and more companies are attempting to offer high-quality gaming experiences on mobile or cheap hardware, offloading the bulk of the rendering workload to powerful

Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) housed within data centres. This approach also has the advantage of decoupling the original software and hardware architecture a game was built to run on from the one of the end user: so long as appropriate input devices are available, an old game built to run on a PowerPC Mac can run on a modern Windows computer, and a game built for a powerful windows PC might run on an Android phone.

Despite these advantages, this approach also poses new challenges: specifically, in order to offer a smooth and responsive experience, control latency (and, to a lesser extent, latency jitter) must be kept to a minimum, at least for fast-paced game genres. While there are techniques to minimize this requirement, e.g. by rendering multiple possible next frames, one per possible combination of user inputs, and sending back only the one that is actually needed, thus shaving the render time from the control loop latency, this requirement is stringent: in order to approximate local delay for a game rendering at 30 Frames Per Seconds (FPSs), which is the minimum accepted standard for smooth gameplay (at least for fast-paced genres), the total interaction delay should not exceed 33ms per frame, including the end-to-end Return Trip Time (RTT) between the user's machine and the DC, the rendering time, and the image encoding/decoding time. Even with the techniques mentioned above, at best this means a requirement of less than 15ms to traverse the path between the DC and the end user in a single direction.

Furthermore, while this approach does not generally require huge amounts of bandwidth per user (about 7Mbps per user using on-the fly compression of 1080p frames, although this has an impact on image quality and further adds to latency), it does generate significant loads on the links between a DC and the access network(s) the end users are attached to.

Requirements: Bandwidth ~7Mbps per user (potentially large on a service linking a DC with the access network); Latency <30ms RTT (including access segment); Availability may be required for premium services; Security not required (authentication taken care of at the application level).

Cloud storage applications

Description: The term “cloud storage” encompasses a host of services which offer remote, typically distributed and redundant, data storage. On one hand, cloud storage services generally offer increased fault tolerance and durability compared to local storage, coupled with the ease of use of a sub-contracted service. On the other hand, remote data storage and access is generally slower and less secure compared to local storage, and requires highly reliable WAN links in order to ensure the availability of the data.

The network requirements of cloud storage can vary widely depending on the specific needs of user: for free, nearly best effort services, like Dropbox or Google Drive, no strict requirement is needed. Companies who opt to store their data remotely might require that their link towards the provider of cloud storage have a certain guaranteed capacity, and reliability characteristics (although those might be best addressed with multiple on-premises WAN-facing routers, to avoid single points of failures).

Requirements: Bandwidth: hundreds of Mbps for Business, none for free; Latency: no guarantee required; Availability: high to very high availability for Business, none for free; Encryption: could be required for Business, taken care of at higher layers for free;

Cloud running applications (e.g. remote computing)

Description: The term “cloud-running application”, generically refers to those applications that run in the cloud environment and require a continuous interaction with the user. The cloud-running applications require a pool of configurable computing resources usually hosted by remote DCs and a reliable communication channel between the user and the remote DC location. An example of cloud-running application is Desktop as a Service (DaaS). DaaS offers a virtual desktop infrastructure hosted by the cloud service provider in its DCs that can be used by customers to access their data and applications from any device. DaaS (and cloud-running applications in general) has stringent requirements in terms of latency (for real-time responsiveness) and reliability. Bandwidth is usually not very stringent, but operations like CAD and video editing are usually not allowed by since they require too much graphics processing.

Requirements: Bandwidth: < 1Mbps per user [DAAS]; Latency: RTT < 90ms; Availability: depends on specific applications, potentially required; Encryption: depends on specific applications, potentially required; Other: packet Loss < 10^{-2} .

Teleconferencing (TID)

Description: There are several companies which have a teleconferencing service to enable a realistic communication between their users/employees. There are rooms with big screens, high quality video and audio, where there are no traffic cuts, but stable connections between the locations of the company.

Requirements: Latency < 10ms, Bandwidth: depends on quality profile (SD or HD), Resolution 1920x1080

2.2.2 Apps related to Machine-based services

Smart metering

Description: Smart metering applications are related to the monitoring of utility services provided to end users, such as water, electricity and gas consumption. Other applications include monitoring of environmental changes and alarm systems. Such devices are attached to metres and sensors and connected to the network, transferring data to centrally located servers or/and end users. Typically, ultra-low data rate signals are transmitted in the order of a few kbps. However, the main characteristic is the massive deployment of such metres which may result to high aggregated bandwidth requirements at the main server and between the server and any processing terminal in the cloud. According to NGMN [NGM5G], the number of metering devices may reach up to 200.000/km², while the connection speed per device may require up to 100kbps.

Future, applications consider increasing the metering intelligence by combining the user’s needs and the environmental conditions. In this case, in addition to metering services, some usage suggestions can be communicated to end users or actions can be taken to optimise the use of resources specially if combined with in house sensors.

Requirements: Massive number of small bandwidth connections, with low system requirements (latency availability). More advanced services require data security and higher availability guaranties.

Surveillance and security (CCTV+ image processing)

Description: surveillance and security applications are mostly related to the capture and processing of video streams. Data is either transferred directly to the end user device or to a main server where it is observed or processed before any notification is sent to the end user. Although, typically, a SD video resolution is acceptable for human controllers, a high video quality is desirable for intelligent machine based processing of video streams, in order to ease face and movement recognition functions and avoid the triggering of false alarms. Apparently, a key characteristic of this application is the required high availability and in some cases the transfer of encrypted data.

A special and interesting application is the access of personal data and home surveillance data/video streams by users while they are on the move and while changing locations over a regional or national network. This requires the establishment of real time encrypted connections, either end-to-end or through a centrally located server.

Requirements: Data bandwidth up to 9Mbps per monitoring channel considering HD video imaging. High availability and data encryption requirements when security issues are involved

Virtual machine migration

Description: Multiple operations in a datacenter environment may require virtual machines (VMs) to be migrated from one server to another or from one DC to another in real-time and without service disruption.

Reasons to do this include:

- Cloud Bursting: VMs are offloaded to a remote DC by enterprise servers, to temporarily increase computational resources available to the enterprise. DC resources are released once the computation finishes.
- Enterprise IT Consolidation: VMs housed in several small enterprise DCs may be moved to one or a few remote bigger DCs, to reduce costs associated with running a DC.
- Follow the Sun: VMs, and their associated data, may be moved throughout the day to be close to whatever part of the world is active at a certain time.
- Disaster Recovery/Preparedness: if significant disruptions are expected for specific DCs (e.g. an incoming hurricane or violent storm is predicted), it is prudent to move critical data and workloads to safer locations until the emergency passes.

In general, migrating live a VM may present a wide range of requirements, from capacity and reliability to pre-scheduling, which largely depend on the exact business purpose of the application(s) running inside that VM. A commercial VM migration technology, developed by VMware, is called vMotion. vMotion moves live, running virtual machines from one host to another while maintaining continuous service availability. It requires latency of <10ms, but with the recently-added Long Distance feature the maximum tolerated latency has been increased to 150ms [LDVM]. Additional information about the requirements for VM migration have been provided by private conversations with cloud industry specialists from Ravello Systems [RAV], which indicate that a typical migration of a large number of VMs at a time will require 10s of Gbps.

Requirements: Bandwidth: 10-100 Gbps; Latency: 10-150ms; Availability: high during active migrations, don't care otherwise; Encryption: potentially useful;

Virtual machine replication

Description: VM replication consists in copying a running VM and keep the two copies (primary and backup) synchronized, to increase redundancy and provide high availability. Two different categories of solutions are possible for keeping the primary and backup VMs synchronized and consistent [PET12]:

- Solutions based on deterministic replay: primary and backup VMs execute at the same time, with non-deterministic events (e.g. interrupts) injected exactly at the same point into both replicas;
- Solutions based on raw state updates: instead of replicating the sequence of instructions on the backup, the primary is checkpointed very frequently and the updates are sent to the backup.

A commercial VM replication tool, developed by VMware, is called vSphere. Bandwidth requirements change widely depending on VM-specific factors such as network-based storage, size of VM dataset and data change rate [VSR]. Moreover, long distances between the primary and backup sites affect replication performance, as well as low packet loss (lower than 1% to have good performance) [VSR2].

Requirements: Bandwidth: hundreds of Mbps to Gbps; Latency: possibly low; Availability: highest affordable; Encryption: possibly useful; Other: low Packet loss $< 10^{-2}$ [VSR2];

DB synchronization

Description: Many modern systems rely on remote distributed databases, for both reliability and performance reasons. Ref. [HUAWP] describes three approaches to guarantee data consistency:

- Active-Standby: a single primary DC is used to serve users, but is synchronized with one or more standby DCs. This is done as a background task, either asynchronously, if inter-DC latency is high, or synchronously, if latency is low enough.
- Single DB instance over multiple DCs: used when a single DC has insufficient infrastructure, and multiple DC have low latency connections, then they can be used as a single logical DC, provided there is also a high-bandwidth, possibly dedicated, DCI WAN link between them. Data is stored in just one DC at a time (no redundancy), so no synchronization is needed.
- Multiple DB instances over multiple DCs: multiple DBs are independently run in multiple, potentially distant DCs. Avoiding data collisions requires support from the application layer. Full bi-directional synchronization of DBs is needed.

The distinction between synchronous DB replication and asynchronous replication is very important as it affects the maximum allowed latency:

- Synchronous replication: every write operation for a transaction must be completed at the replicated server before the transaction is done and the active server can continue running the code

- Asynchronous replication: Upon write operation during a transaction, the active server proceeds with further processing while the system moves the data to the remote server for replication.

Clearly, latency is crucial to synchronous replication, since the speed of processing by the active server depends on it. This is not the case for asynchronous replication. The exact requirements that DB synchronization places on the transport network depend on a number of factors: DB topology (affects required capacity and latency), updates rate (affects required latency) and whether the system is synchronous or asynchronous (affects required latency, and potentially capacity and duration).

Requirements: Bandwidth: potentially hundreds of Mbps; Latency: lowest possible for synchronous; Availability: highest for Synchronous, potentially high for Asynchronous; Encryption: potentially useful but not generally required;

2.2.3 Apps related to advanced new services emerging from 5G

New network technologies, often collectively referred to as “5G”, will unlock opportunities for different types of advanced new applications. The improved network performance in terms of e.g. bitrates, latency and reliability, mainly enabled by new access technology, and fast and efficient provisioning and slicing enabled by NFV and SDN are the key enabling technologies for advanced applications emerging in the 5G ecosystem.

HD video live streaming and sharing in events

Description: This case is related to the provisioning of advanced media services in crowded areas, with the purpose to enhance the offered services and experience of the participating users. Such events are related with sports games, concerts or open air festivals. Additional services offered may include: live streaming of various angle views, replays, sharing of videos and comments by users. The key characteristic of these applications is the huge bandwidth and low latency demands that are generated for a small amount of time (i.e. during the event) and are concentrated over a specific area.

Requirements: Bandwidth requirements: 40Mb/s/user for 4K or 90Mb/s/user for 8K streams. Latency requirement is critical for good experience (but not for replays). Security requirements are limited primarily to registration and authentication of user subscriptions. Mobility requirements are very limited.

Augmented and Virtual Reality (gaming, entertainment)

Description: Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) applications are considered one of the main drivers in future gaming and entertainment industry, imposing strict network requirements with respect to latency, availability security and bandwidth. Applications would typically require connectivity to a main server which should ensure synchronicity and accurate user position. Real environment applications, (i.e. AR applications) use the actual environment, which is enhanced with additional (virtual) information for gaming purposes or interactive entertainment scopes or even educational and commercial purposes. In VR environment a complete scene is streamed and adapted to the user position in it with additional information from other users accessing the same environment.

Requirements: AR bandwidth requirements are relaxed since the real environment is used. In this case mobility requirements and coverage are important, since certain gaming applications may lead to a large

number of users concentrated in a certain area and moving around it. Bandwidth requirements are becoming critical in VR environments requesting multiples of HD video streams to be combined for 360-degrees view. This may reach up to 8x the video quality (e.g. 40Mbps for 4K or 9Mbps for HD) for certain applications. Latency is a critical requirement for synchronicity purposes and should be kept below 20ms for good user experience. Security is typically limited to user registration and authentication unless online purchasing options and VR shopping applications are considered.

Tactile Internet

Description: The Tactile Internet, by a strict definition, is a system where a human controls physical or real objects by tactile input and receives tactile, audio, or visual feedback [TR22862]. The feedback should be fast enough to give the impression of zero-latency control. According to [TACT], the Tactile Internet will be more generally defined by extremely low latency in combination with high availability, reliability and security.

Requirements: From [NGMN5G]: Latency: <1 ms, Bitrate DL: 50 Mbps, UL: 25 Mbps

Telepresence

Description: Telepresence allows a person to feel as if they were present at a live real-world location other than their physical location. Someone experiencing telepresence would be able to behave, and receive stimuli, as though part of a meeting at the remote site. Additionally, users may be given the ability to affect the remote location. A related concept is virtual presence, where telepresence is combined with virtual/augmented reality technologies, enabling virtual meeting rooms.

Requirements: From [TR22863]: Latency: 10-12 ms. Bitrate: 250 Mbps (should be capable of running 8k 3D video streaming for uplink and downlink)

Industrial control

Description: Industrial factory automation requires communications for closed-loop control applications, where a controller interacts with a number of sensors and actuators. An example application is control of industrial robots used for manufacturing. Industrial process automation requires communications for both supervisory and open-loop control applications, as well as process monitoring and tracking operations inside an industrial plant. In these applications, a large number of sensors that are distributed over the plant forward measurement data to process controllers.

Requirements: From [TR22862]: Extreme industrial control: Latency: 0.25 ms. Reliability: 99.9999999%

Conventional industrial control: Latency: 1 ms (can be longer, e.g. 8 ms, for some applications). Reliability: 99.999%. Bitrate: 10 Mbps per device uplink and downlink

Industrial automation: Latency: 25 ms, Reliability: 99.999%

Remote surgery

Description: Remote surgery allows a surgeon to operate a surgical robot to perform surgery on a patient even though they are not physically in the same location. This generally involves a communication link for

command and control of one or more robotic arms as well as a sensory system giving feedback to the user (e.g. video and audio feeds).

Requirements: From [NGMNVI] Latency: 10-100 ms Bitrate: Up to 1 Mbps for control commands, ~100 Mbps for live video feed

Connected vehicles

Description: Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication is the exchange of information between a vehicle and any entity that may affect (or be affected by) the vehicle. It includes communication with other vehicles (V2V), roadside infrastructure (V2I), pedestrians (V2P), and backend servers on the network (V2N). One application is assisted driving, where the driver is given useful information (e.g. road hazards or vulnerable road users) to better manoeuvre the vehicle. Another application is autonomous/cooperative driving, where varying degrees of driver involvement can be envisaged up to full automation where recognition, decision-making and manoeuvring are performed solely by the vehicle. Fully autonomous vehicles can cooperate to different degrees ranging from information exchange about intentions (e.g. for overtaking) to fully synchronized driving where intentions are constantly exchanged and cooperative decisions are made and constantly updated (e.g. platooning).

Requirements:

For V2X for cooperation (coordinated control), from [NGMNVI]: Latency: <3 ms for platooning, <10 ms for cooperative manoeuvres, <100 ms for coarse driving intention. Reliability: 99.999% Bitrate: 5 Mbps per link

2.3 Summary of the application characterization

The applications presented in the previous sub-section are summarized in the following table. Their characteristics with respect to bandwidth (data rate), latency, availability, and security requirements are highlighted. These requirements are the typical ones expected from the various applications and according to the majority of the traffic generated by each application. Also any assumptions made, consider traffic demands and key technologies that are expected to be available in 2020 (e.g. higher penetration of 4K and 8K video services). In some cases specific requirements may apply depending on the end user agreements or the type of data that are exchanged.

Bandwidth requirements are characterized according to the expected data rate per user and the assumed concentration of active users or devices (i.e. combination of coverage and active usage) in urban network segments or as specified by the application. The estimated total data rate requirement is extracted representing the aggregated bandwidth demand at the backbone (metro/core) segment. Moreover, three categories are defined for latency, availability and security requirements according to their importance.

Table 2-1: Summary of the application characterization.

	Requirements	Bandwidth	Latency	Availability	Security	Remarks
	Applications	- data rate per user - user coverage* - usage (% of users) - total bandwidth	Low: <1s Important: 20-100ms Critical:<10ms	Low: 0x9s Important: 3-5x9s Critical: >7x9s	Some: reg. + authentication High: data encryption	
Broadband and cloud –based services	OTT video services	8-90Mbps Upto 10000/km ² Up to 25% use 20-200Gbps	Low	Low	No	Rate per user refer to HD, 4K, 8K video.
	Content Delivery Network	40-90Mbps Upto 10000/km ² Up to 25% use 20-200Gbps	Low	Important	Some	Coverage refers to dense urban scenarios. Currently high market penetration for OTT services leads to large aggregated rates in core. Increase in CDN will decrease OTT in future.
	Broadcasting (Live TV)	8-90Mbps Upto 10000/km ² Up to 25% use 20-200Gbps	Low	Low	No	
	Cloud gaming	7-10Mbps Up to xx/km ² Up to xx% xx Gbps	Important <30ms	Important (for registered services)	No or Some	
	Cloud storage applications	10-300Mbps Free services Up to xx/km ² Up to xx% xx Gbps	Low	Low	Some (for personal use) High (for professional)	Free services (dropbox, drive) with no special treatment but high traffic demands. Professional services may have strict requirements in data rate and security
	Cloud running applications	Up to 1Mbps Low total BW requirements	Important <80ms	Low	Some	Stringent requirements in terms of latency and reliability. Usually low bandwidth requirements, but it depends on the application.
	Teleconferencing	8-40Mbps Low total BW requirements	Important <40ms	Important	Some (High upon request for data transfer)	
Machine-based services	Smart metering	<1Mbps ~10k-100k/km ² Small usage but with picks Up to 10Gbps	Low	Low (for utilities) Important (for damage monitoring)	No	Low bandwidth requirements, but may increase if feedback services are considered for optimum use (e.g. energy saving)
	Surveillance and security	~9Mbps (HD res) Up to 1000/km ² Up to 50% use	Important ~100ms		High (data integrity and privacy issues)	Total traffic increase by x4 to x10 if 4K or 8K is required

* For broadband services, this is the combination of the average population density in dense urban regions in Europe (~12000/km²) and the average expected penetration of smartphone devices per user by 2020 (~80%)

Requirements Applications	Bandwidth	Latency	Availability	Security	Remarks
	- data rate per user - user coverage* - usage (% of users) - total bandwidth	Low: <1s Important: 20-100ms Critical:<10ms	Low: 0x9s Important: 3-5x9s Critical: >7x9s	Some: reg. + authentication High: data encryption	
	2-5Gbps total				Importance level for requirements increases if guidance services or critical sensing is involved.
Virtual machine migration	Applies only between DCs 10-100Gbps total bandwidth	Important 10ms-150ms	Critical	High	High availability is required to avoid data losses. Security issues are related primarily with data integrity.
Virtual machine replication	Applies only between DCs	Important 10-30ms	Critical	High	
HD video streaming and sharing in events	40-90Mbps Events up to 50k people/km ² ~10% usage 100-300Gbps total bandwidth	Important <30ms	Low (for free services) Important (for registered)	No (free) Some (registered)	Possible to have large peaks in demands during events reaching even x5 the bandwidth requirements assumed
Augmented Reality	1-5Mbps Up to 1000 users /km ² Up to 1-5Gbps total	Important <30ms	Low (for free services) Important (for registered)	No (free) Some (registered) High (secure transactions)	Assume multiple gaming or entertainment events or shopping services over a certain area
Virtual Reality	50-250Mbps Up to 1000 users /km ² Up to 200Gbps total	Important <20ms (Critical)	Low (for free services) Important (for registered)	No (free) Some (registered) High (secure transactions)	Security levels depend on type of offered services
Tactile Internet	<50Mbps Up to xx Gbps total	Critical 1-3ms	Important (Critical)	Some (High)	Availability and security may increase to critical and high level for certain applications which control sensitive or vital procedures
Telepresence	50-250Mbps Up to 100 users in business area Up to 20Gb/s total	Critical <10ms	Critical	High	High concentration of services is expected at business areas Assume 3D or 360° video for maximum experience
Industrial control	1-10Mbps per control element For a few up to 1000 elements Up to 1-5Gb/s total	Critical <1ms (for control) Important ~25ms (for automation)	Critical (for control)	High	
Remote surgery		Important (<20ms)	Critical	High	
Connected vehicles		Critical <3ms	Critical	High	

Advanced 5G services

3 Overview of the ACINO architecture and the application aware multi-layer operations

This section describes the ACINO architecture and the supported operations. Emphasis is given on the application aware characteristics and functions of the ACINO controller.

3.1 ACINO orchestrator overview

The ACINO concept is based on allowing certain applications to specify explicitly the requirements for the network services they need, in terms of high-level primitives or intents; in this document, we use the following definitions:

- Primitive: a parameter that expresses a service feature, e.g. network object or constraint;
- Intent: a combination of desired primitives that corresponds to the desired characteristics of a useful service.

In other words, in line with existing literature on the subject, we refer to “primitives” when describing one or more features of the underlying network(s) that the ACINO orchestrator is able to handle, and we call “intents” a combination of primitives that a client application selects to describe the desired characteristics of a service.

At a high level, the ACINO architecture is based on a logically centralized **Orchestrator**, outlined in Figure 3.1, with the primary function of translating application-level service requirements into appropriate configuration requests for both the underlying IP/MPLS and Optical network layers. This involves several sub-processes, including: maintaining a multi-layer model of the controlled network, using it to determine which resources are available to serve new connections and selecting resources that satisfy application-level constraints (expressed by means of “intents”), which include instantiating additional connections in the supporting optical layer if needed. Furthermore, the orchestrator houses an online planning tool, which allows the simulation of the effect of various changes in the network, such as failures, new services and network re-optimizations.

The orchestrator interfaces with the outside world through two main interfaces. Firstly, via a **North-Bound Interface** (NBI) towards applications, which gives them the possibility to request network services with specific requirements, such as latency, reliability and capacity. Special applications, such as a Network Management System (NMS), may even interface with the online planning functionalities exposed by the orchestrator. These “application intents” are then translated into a multi-layer service configuration utilizing both IP/MPLS and optical resources, which is pushed down to the underlying network layers through the use of a **South-Bound Interface** (SBI), which connects the orchestrator to the control planes of both the optical and the IP networks, and is used to both push configuration and pull network state or relevant alarm states from the networks being controlled.

The rest of this section briefly outlines the major components of this architecture, as seen from outside; a more detailed representation of the internal modules is detailed in deliverable D3.1.

Figure 3.1: Simplified schema of the ACINO orchestrator.

Orchestrator

The ACINO orchestrator is a platform that performs the following functions: (i) it gathers information on the underlying network layers using the SBI and stores it into a multi-layer network model; (ii) it receives service requests from applications through the NBI in the form of “intents”, maps these intents into installable configuration for the underlying networks, optimizing it with respect to both the explicit service requirements (which must be satisfied, if at all possible) and existing configuration (re-using pre-established lightpaths and Traffic Engineering tunnels whenever possible), and pushes such configuration down to the underlying network control planes via the SBI, and (iii) it receives planning requests from one or more Network Management System class application through the NBI, computes the effects of the proposed changes and replies back to the requestor with the outcomes of the computation; optionally, it may also push the resulting configuration to the underlying network layer via the SBI.

North-Bound Interface (NBI)

The North-Bound intent-based Interface allows a “network-aware” application to request a network service (i.e., connectivity) by explicitly specifying both standard parameters, such as ingress and egress points, and also several metrics that affect the quality and type of service it perceives, capacity (bandwidth), reliability, maximum latency and more. Additionally, it allows the interfacing of an application such as a NMS with an internal online planning tool. This tool allows to examine the consequences of possible changes in the configuration of the underlying networks in a dynamic fashion, and to re-optimize the current configuration in order to, e.g., minimize a cost or performance metric.

South-Bound Interface (SBI)

The south-bound interface is used by the orchestrator to interface with the control planes of the underlying IP/MPLS and Optical layers.

Irrespective of the exact technology used, the purpose of this interface is to enable both pulling topological information from the underlying layers, and pushing configuration commands to (eventually) the underlying devices.

3.2 Multi-layer Connections Configuration

This sub-section describes various approaches for configuring multi-layer connections. In all these, we assume that the operator wishes to set up a new IP link using an underlying optical connection.

3.2.1 Provisioning

Create a link between two routers, and the underlying optical path via the multi-layer orchestrator by selecting the router end points. In this case, the optical path for the IP link is not constrained.

3.2.2 Explicit Route Provisioning

Create IP links using optical connections via the multi-layer orchestrator, based on the needs of the IP layer. In this case the orchestrator attempts to compute the optimal route for this connection to achieve the following (often conflicting) goals:

1. Maximum diversity constraint: an optical failure that affects the new IP link and other IP links must minimize the total impacted IP traffic and overall need for extra capacity in the IP layer
2. Maximum latency constraint: the latency of the new IP link must allow the necessary low latency traffic to use it
3. Optical cost constraint: the optical cost of the new path must be low – for example, avoiding unnecessary regeneration, or selecting a wavelength that minimizes wavelength blocking in the network.

After figuring out the optimal path, the orchestrator requests this explicit path from the optical network.

3.2.3 Route Restricted Provisioning

Create IP links using optical connections via the multi-layer orchestrator, based on the needs of the IP layer. As in the previous case, the orchestrator attempts to compute the optimal route for this connection to achieve the same goals, however it cannot directly provision the explicit path in the optical layer. Instead it expresses the required constraints in terms of optical nodes, links and SRLGs to use or to avoid. This is harder to figure out, since it requires a more general view of the main constraints that drive to the optical path for the IP layer, but it gives the optical layer more leeway in selecting the path.

3.2.4 Service Resilience Provisioning

Create IP links using connection with optical service resilience (either protection or restoration). In this case, the orchestrator must not only specify the constraints of the working path, but also the constraints for the protection/restoration path. These are fundamentally the same constraints, except that they may be relaxed for the protection/restoration path, due to the temporary use of this path. For example, the max diversity constraint is not so important if the operator is not worried about another failure during the time of the first failure.

3.2.5 Bandwidth Provisioning

Modify the bandwidth of an IP link based on traffic trends in the IP layer. This results in a request for the optical layer to modify the bandwidth it provides to the IP layer. Such a bandwidth change can translate into 1) a larger ODU container in case of an underlying OTN network, 2) a change in modulation format, or addition of optical subcarriers, if the optical connection supports flexible rate transponders, or 3) the addition of another fixed-rate wavelength to a multi-link IP adjacency (called “link bundle”). Such changes also impact the IP layer – in case of TE networks, the capacity of the link is disseminated to all routers to allow rerouting of MPLS tunnels. In case of L2 link bundles (LAG), there is a need to add the new link to the bundle.

3.2.6 Traffic Engineering Re-Routing

The IP layer periodically re-optimizes TE tunnels – implying their rerouting over a better path from the MPLS-TE perspective. Multi-layer orchestration will not directly influence such rerouting, as this is purely the business of the IP/MPLS layers (and their single-layer controllers).

Multi-layer orchestration does attempt to optimize optical paths so as to better support the IP layer. Whenever an opportunity is identified to substantially improve a connection with respect to one of the above-specified constraints, the orchestrator must find a way for a hitless move of the optical connection to the improved path. This must be done in close collaboration with the IP layer. First, the orchestrator must understand if the IP layer can support shutting down the link supported by this optical connection without creating congestion elsewhere. Second, the IP link must be taken out gracefully – either by increasing its IGP metric or by removing it from a link bundle. Only then, once traffic no longer uses the IP link, can its optical path be changed. Once the new path is up, the reverse process happens and the link is put back in service.

3.3 Multi-layer failure handling

Considering interactions between IP and transmission control plane, higher layer has the possibility to set up automatically some adjacencies in case of network failures, providing automated network reconfiguration. This use case potentially applies to any IP network relying on a WDM / OTN network. UNI interfaces between IP and optical networks enable requesting for connections on demand, after a failure happens in the IP layer. This allows minimizing the number of IP resources for backup purposes. Similarly, this procedure can be done from a SDN controller.

In traditional hierarchical IP networks where protection is handled through parities, the network dimensioning savings we can expect from such approach is limited to the interfaces that interconnect the routers of the 2 parities. Optical restoration (and possibly 1:N protection of the interfaces) does not really help saving interfaces on the routers since we still need to protect them against equipment failures (duplicated redundant configurations). Such approach implies to continuously monitor the state of the network in order to plan the upgrades that might be required by the traffic growth, as network resources can be used autonomously with potentially no human confirmation.

Figure 3.2: Multi-layer IP-port resilient mechanism.

On the other hand, multilayer resilience mechanisms could enable network operators to optimize IP backup resources since just a free IP port would be required in each node to recover any port failure in the router.

A main drawback of these multilayer resilience schemes is the recovery time since the whole service cannot be restored until the light-path is established. As a result, this kind of restoration mechanism can only be applied to best-effort traffic without strict recovery times. On the other hand, a combination of 1+1 and multilayer resilience could enable network operators to extend the time to repair a failure in the IP layer.

3.4 Multi-layer Shared Backup Router

The Multi-layer Shared Backup Router (MLSBR) use case was presented in [MUN12]. The idea behind MLSBR consists on having extra-shared backup routers to restore the traffic in case of a failure of an IP router. This technique compared with the common design of today's networks, where two IP planes are created in order to deal with node failure, reduces the investment in IP routers [MAY14].

In MLSBR it is assumed that there is an optical mesh connection access, transit and interconnection routers. Let us assume a hierarchical architecture with three levels, as shown in Figure 3.3a. In this example, the transit routers are duplicated to recover to a transit failure. When using MLSBR, a set of Shared Backup Routers (SBRs) are available so, when there is a failure in the transit routers, the failed transit router configuration is copied and new connections are created to the access and interconnection nodes. This scheme is presented in Figure 3.3b. To create the IP/MPLS adjacencies from the access routers to the backup routers, a new optical connection is created between the corresponding optical endpoints. The destination back-up router and the path to be requested is configured beforehand by the access router. Similar configuration is also performed for the backup transit router and the interconnection router. As previously mentioned, it is assumed that there is an optical mesh between access and transit nodes. This is why a new back-up path can be provisioned after the failure happens. Let us remark that the recovery time using dual-plane protection resilient is faster than applying MLBSR, because MLBSR takes similar time to optical restoration.

Figure 3.3: Resilience schemes in a hierarchical topology.

4 Use cases

Some realistic applications and relevant network operations have been selected to illustrate the value proposition of SDN in application centric IP/optical networks. These applications are defined in 6 use cases which are used highlight the necessity of the application aware routing in multi-layer IP-Optical network and the added value that can be brought to the operators.

4.1 Application-based Datacentre Interconnection

The most basic use case for the ACINO approach is that of a network-aware application requiring a service with specific characteristics. Many examples of such applications are given in section 2 of this document. One case study is that of Cloud applications which require inter-DC connectivity. As explained in more detail in Section 2.2.2, different cloud applications can have significantly different requirements.

Consider, for example, the following set of applications/services:

- A. A business application needs to migrate VMs according to a “follow the sun” approach, which entails regular, schedulable, large-sized, short lived network flows for which latency is not paramount.
- B. A set of resources over two DCs is logically unified in a single pool, which requires a dedicated DCI link and some guaranteed (large) bandwidth on demand over it.
- C. An application consisting of a distributed, synchronously updated DB, requires a constant low bit rate connection with minimal latency.
- D. A customer uses the DC as caching point for video distribution, serving data to customers and periodically (e.g. every day in the early morning) refreshing the contents of the cache based on expected requests. This is a schedulable flow, requiring high bandwidth for a specific, limited amount of time.

Assume these applications make their service requests in order, involving the following DCs: A between DC₁ and DC₂, B between DC₂ and DC₃, C and D between DC₁ and DC₃ (see Figure 4.1). Furthermore, applications A and D are time-schedulable, and their requested schedules are “compatible”, as follows: application A requires connectivity from t_0 to t_1 , while application D requires connectivity from t_2 to t_3 , with $t_0 < t_1 < t_2 < t_3$ and $t_{24h} > (t_3 - t_0)$.

Given the bandwidth and end-points requirements, and topology depicted in Figure 4.1, any network control plane would be able to map application A an IP adjacency (TE Link) between DC₁ and DC₂, and possibly re-use that and a further adjacency used by application B between DC₂ and DC₃ to serve the traffic of applications C and D, all on a largely permanent basis. While this approach works, it has several shortcomings: the first adjacency, between DC₁ and DC₂, would have to be dimensioned to carry traffic from three applications simultaneously, although in fact A and D operate on non-intersecting time periods, so only the capacity to support the larger of the two is needed. The use of a second adjacency between DC₂ and DC₃ minimizes the number of necessary interfaces, but also does not cater to the demands of C, for which there exists a (physically) shorter path directly between DC₁ and DC₃, as shown in Figure 4.1.

Using the ACINO approach, these applications could explicitly specify their requirements, which would lead to the following considerations: application A just requires connectivity between DC₁ and DC₂, as does application B, albeit between DC₂ and DC₃. Application C requires minimal latency, and would likely specify a maximum amount of latency it can tolerate. If this is high enough to go the R1-R2-R3 route, and there is enough spare capacity on the TE links setup for A and B, then this application could be served by re-using those by chaining them via IP or even OTN. Otherwise, a single lightpath would need to be created on the physically shortest path between DC₁ and DC₃, using yet another set of transceivers to satisfy this application.

Lastly, depending on how application A and C were served, application D may be served by either re-using one transceiver occupied by A's dedicated lightpath, or by co-opting the (likely ample, given the low bandwidth requirement) spare capacity on C's.

Figure 4.1: Application centric Intent-based IP optical orchestration.

In addition, in a more loaded scenario where network resources are scarce, it may happen that there is no way for the network to ensure that all requirements specified by an upcoming application are met (not even by globally re-optimizing its configuration). In such a case, the ACINO approach proposes to allow a negotiation to occur between the network and the requesting application. As an example, assume that the request from application D in the scenario described cannot be fulfilled as the amount of bandwidth requested cannot be reserved for it without impacting the services for the other applications. In such a situation, the network would reply offering the best (highest) possible parameter it can offer, in this case the amount of bandwidth it is able (or willing) to provide for this service. The application would then either accept the proposed service or reject it, based on its knowledge of its own requirements.

4.2 Enabling dynamic 5G services

Dense deployments of small cells, often referred to as ultra-dense networks (UDN), will be a major building block for increasing radio access capacity in 5G [NGM5G]. UDN is also one of the main topics in the EU project METIS [METD11, METD65], whose objective is to lay the foundations for 5G.

The scenario considered here is a UDN deployed in a location where a large crowd of people is gathered in a relatively small area for limited time periods, and where all the small cells are switched off the rest of the time. The application from ACINO's perspective is then to dynamically provide backhaul capacity for the UDN when it is active, either as a single application, or as multiple applications by offering differentiated services for different traffic flows. One example, illustrated in Figure 4.2, is a stadium where the UDN is active for the duration of a live event, such as a football match or a concert.

The stadium scenario was studied in METIS [METIS], where the considered deployment is a dense network of small cell antennas installed at the rooftop of the stadium and connected with optical fibre to a common baseband unit, which is then connected to a gateway that provides access to the Mobile Network Operator's (MNO) core network [METD65].

Figure 4.2: Illustration of a UDN deployment at a stadium (from [METD65]).

Regarding the application characterization, the main issue with the stadium scenario, as well as other dynamic UDN scenarios, is that the traffic is a mix of different applications from different end users. From the ACINO network perspective there are two alternatives: either 5G backhaul traffic is treated as coming from a single network application, with requirements given by the MNO, or it is separated based on application already at the stadium site, before entering the ACINO network. In the first scenario, the 5G network benefits from the ACINO approach through e.g. the ability to dynamically request and reserve bandwidth. This could be either in real-time with dynamic renegotiation of the already allocated bandwidth resources or it could be through pre-planned scheduling of additional resource reservation ahead of time, for example to coincide with a large planned event. The single application consisting of all the 5G backhaul

traffic in this case also benefits from the ACINO ability to apply strict bandwidth and latency constraints, enabling the sharing of the ACINO network between 5G traffic and other traffic. However, as the 5G network aims to support several different types of services, some with high bandwidth requirements and others with requirements on low latency and reliability, the single ACINO application class has to cover all the cases. The result is that a single high bandwidth, reliable, low latency connection has to be established, likely at a high cost.

The second alternative, classifying applications with different requirements within the 5G network as separate application-classes in ACINO, is likely a better approach. In this case, separate application connections meeting different requirements can be established. For example, one application could be for remote control of camera drones filming the event and transmission of their video streams to a central production studio. This application has requirements on low latency and high reliability, and likely on security as well, e.g. for making it more difficult for a hostile party to take control of the remote controlled drones. Another application, expected to dominate the traffic volume in the stadium case, could be supporting the video and photo uploads / downloads from members in the audience, with higher requirements on bandwidth but less focus on latency and reliability. A third application could be connecting a number of different environmental sensors at the stadium to a central location with low requirements on bandwidth and no strict latency requirements. Mapping these three applications to table 2.5, the video upload/download would be a sub-class of the eMBB category, remote control of drones would correspond to critical MTC, and the sensors would correspond to massive MTC. Establishing separate connections for the three applications, with different requirements on bandwidth, latency and reliability, is likely less costly than the combined service in the case with a single 5G backhaul application.

Network slicing has emerged as a service deployment concept in 5G, that enables the sharing of a physical infrastructure between use cases with very different requirements by introducing multiple virtual and logically separated instances from radio access, through transport, to core networks [NGM5G],[NGMNS]. Even though it is not clear yet exactly how network slicing will be implemented, it fits well with a scenario where different application-classes in the ACINO network is used for different 5G services.

The scenario with multiple applications per 5G network is depicted in Figure 4.3, where a mobile edge cloud, running distributed 5G core functions and potentially some applications is located at or close to the stadium. From the edge cloud, a high bandwidth connection has been established to a data center (e.g. YouTube) for video upload/download traffic. A separate connection for applications requiring low latency and high reliability (e.g. remote control and voice traffic) has been established to the mobile core cloud. Finally, a third low bandwidth connection has been established for sensor data. Note that in practice at least one other connection would have to be established for other best-effort internet access.

The predicted required aggregated traffic volumes for the stadium scenario as well as for an office UDN deployment are given in [NGM5G] and listed in Table 4-1 below. Other dynamic UDN scenarios considered in [METD11] are an open air festival and a shopping mall. Predicted traffic volumes for these scenarios from [METD11] are also listed in Table 4-1. The predicted traffic volumes are high enough to fill multiple wavelengths or sub-wavelengths within optical channels.

Figure 4.3: Illustration of traffic separation based on application in the access node located at the UDN deployment site.

For all the scenarios, Table 4-1 also shows the expected dominating application as well as time scales for when the UDN is active. The dominating traffic is expected to flow between the UDN and a datacenter, which could be regional, national or even international. The end-to-end latency requirement is listed as 10ms in [NGM5G]. There is no clear need for protection/restoration or network encryption in any of the scenarios, except possibly for the office.

Table 4-1: Predicted aggregated traffic volumes for the stadium scenario and an office UDN deployment [NGM5G].

Requirement	Stadium	Festival	Shopping mall	Office
Dominating application	Video/photo sharing (upload) + video streaming (download)	Similar to stadium? + "Internet access"	Augmented reality?	Cloud storage
Capacity	DL: 750 Gbps UL: 1500 Gbps	DL+UL: 900 Gbps	DL: 34 Gbps UL: 13 Gbps (assuming 0.2 km ²)	DL: 15 Gbps UL: 2 Gbps
Time scales	2-3 events per week 2-3 hours per event	1-2 events per year lasting for 1-4 days	Opening hours, e.g. 10-18 every day	Office hours
Distance	Regional to international	Regional to international	Regional to international	Regional to international
Latency	10ms e2e	10ms e2e	10ms e2e	10ms e2e
Protection/ Restoration	Desirable	Desirable	Desirable	Maybe required?
Encryption	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe

4.3 Application-specific protection strategies

Optical layer restoration and multi-layer restoration have been discussed in the literature. It has been shown that they can account for very substantial savings – as show in the figure below (based [GER14]).

In both cases, it is assumed that some of the responsibility for restoring from failures in the optical layer is moved to the optical layer, since it is much more cost effective to build in spare capacity in the optical layer than to do so in the IP layer. The former approach assumes that the optical layer alone is responsible for restoring from the failure – and therefore the selection of the restoration path is insensitive to the needs of the IP layer. The latter approach does take IP layer needs into account, but for the aggregate traffic that traverses the failed IP links.

Several application-specific constraints are relevant for restoration. We consider here two who have different implications for the design of the restoration scheme:

1. Maximum allowable outage time.
2. Maximum allowable latency.

Figure 4.4: Savings due to multi-layer strategies.

The first constraint affects the use of optical restoration for the application: since optical restoration is slow (tens of seconds at best for a large network), such an outage may be too long for outage-sensitive traffic. Such traffic should be restored in the IP layer immediately – before optical restoration kicks in. Its path may be later re-optimized to the use of the optically-restored IP link – this is typical behaviour of the IP layer. This constraint means that the IP layer must have sufficient spare capacity to support such outage-sensitive traffic, without relying on the optical layer. Hence, it affects the sizing of the IP links under failure.

The second constraint affects the type of traffic that will traverse the restored link in steady state (not just in the first few minutes after the outage). If the restored optical path causes the overall path of latency-sensitive

traffic to be too long, then the traffic will never be re-optimized to use the restored link. Therefore, the restored link will not have to carry such traffic and can be sized lower than what it needs to be during normal conditions. The following table summarizes these two types of constraints and how they will impact the use of optically-restored capacity:

Table 4-2: Constraints for of optically-restored capacity.

Constraint	Wait for optical restoration?	Re-optimize to use optically restored path?
Max outage time	No – restore in the IP Layer	Yes
Max latency	OK to wait for the optical layer	Traffic that meeting the ‘max latency’ requirement, should not re-optimized.

An example for the behaviour of latency-sensitive traffic can be found below. In this example, we assume all optical links have the same length and that a service can tolerate a latency of 4 optical links. Figure 4.5 shows a service routed over this network in green (on the left), and its routing over the network after the optical recovery from a failure (in the middle), assuming it takes the same IP layer path. This is OK for non-latency-sensitive traffic, however if the max latency is 4 hops, then the IP layer should route the service over a different IP path – as shown in the right-most figure.

Figure 4.5: Solutions to deal with a failure in a multi-layer scenario.

4.4 Secure Transmission as a Service

The frequency of cyber-attacks on critical network infrastructure and public/private entities connected to the Internet has been growing significantly and has translated into significant financial costs for end-customers or businesses. Based on a survey conducted with various institutions in the US as seen in Figure 4.6, a significant percentage of entities in various sectors encountered different levels of cyber-security attacks. Based on the same report, each institution on average faced 135 security incidents per year, and for about 33% of the respondents who could estimate the financial cost of cyber-security attacks, the average annual monetary loss was about \$415,000 per institution.

As a result, more and more businesses are investing in improving their security infrastructure. One of the most common trends for securing the communication has been to push for end-to-end encryption (IPSec,

HTTPS). As of July 13, 2015 (see Figure 4.7), 21.3% of the 145,631 sites surveyed support HTTPS, and 4.2% support HTTP Strict Transport Security. End-to-end encryption is very flexible and independent of the underlying network infrastructure, and as a result relatively easy to deploy. However, the flexibility comes at the cost of increased processing requirements at both the server and client endpoints, increased latency and reduced throughput from the network.

At the same time, server-to-server communication, especially data centre interconnects (DCI) are increasingly becoming a lucrative service offering for network operators. The data-centre interconnect market is expected to increase by approximately 100% by 2019, making it a lucrative market for service providers to offer differentiated services. In the DCI application, the endpoints (data-centres) are trusted entities, and as a result, the responsibility of securing the communication can be moved away from the actual endpoints to the network infrastructure. Shifting the responsibility reduces the processing complexity at the endpoints (servers) and allows network operators to optimize the \$/bit cost for encrypting traffic between two remote sites. Different mechanisms such as IPSec, IEEE MacSec, and custom all-optical encryption³ differ on the cost of deployment, availability, latency and throughput.

Figure 4.6: Percent of respondents reporting cyber attacks¹ based on a survey of more than 500 executives of US businesses, law enforcement services, and government agencies (Multiple answers allowed per question).

Figure 4.7: Datacenter interconnect market forecast (Ovum DCI Market Forecast Nov'14).

Table 4-3: Comparison of different encryption mechanisms

Requirement	IPSec	MACSec (L2)	Layer 1 (ADVA ConnectGuard)
Latency	high	medium	low
Data Throughput	low	medium	line speed (no overhead)
Protocol Transparency	low	medium	high
Flexible Encrypted Payload Size	restricted	restricted (standard MAC size)	1G – 100G
End-to-End Compatibility	IP only	layer 2 only	Fiber/OTN SONET/SDH
Flexibility (Meshed)	high	low	medium

The distinctive features of these technologies provide an opportunity for the network operators to differentiate their service portfolio to meet the needs of specific applications. For example, for dynamic low volume interconnects between two or more sites in a meshed configuration, secure connectivity can be established by setting up IPSec tunnels between the sites, while applications such as interconnects between financial institutions, that are extremely sensitive to latency, or large dataset transfers, that are extremely sensitive to throughput, can employ all-optical encryption that requires custom infrastructure (and is therefore a limited resource).

4.5 Dynamic Virtual CDN deployment

In general, an operator's network comprises three parts (see Figure 4.8): an access network, a Metropolitan Area Network (MAN) and the IP core. This means that traffic processing at the IP layer starts at the Broadband Network Gateway (BNG). BNGs are redundantly deployed for every 32K to 96K users. Content delivery networks (CDN) are used to deliver content from servers located in data centers (DCs) to end users. In this case, we will consider video distribution as a reference application for the CDNs. Videos are delivered by using the IP layer. Therefore, the choices for an operator's CDN location are limited to the IP core. Possible deployment sites include regional DCs at the access routers (AR), high density DCs at the transit routers (TR) or even national DCs at the interconnection level (IX). Deployment of video applications only on National CDN has the advantage of high utilization of the video servers, since users access the same data centers, thus statistically using the resources more often. However, each connection or video between the user and one of those national video servers would pass the whole national network. As the data flows are unicast for video on demand or time shifted services, the (redundant) overhead in the network would be massive. On the other hand, the video servers deployed at the BNG locations minimize the network overhead, but increase the video platform's costs by increasing the number of locations and redundant copies of the same content. Moreover, if the number of customers using these video servers is small, the dimensioning and caching is not efficient.

This situation can be solved along two dimensions. The first one is to work on a better planning for the BNG's and video servers' locations. However, as the traffic nature is dynamic (events in stadiums, popular contents in regions, unexpected high penetration...), the second and complementary option is to deploy a virtual CDN infrastructure. The virtual CDN infrastructure has the same capabilities as current CDN deployments, but it runs in standard x86 servers. This way the vCDN provider can dynamically activate VMs in locations that require more video servers. Once the video server is activated, the contents can be transferred from a national/regional data center to sync the most popular content. This requires an inter-data center transfer, which will require network resources for a one time sync between the fixed and the virtual CDN site. This approach can reuse the investment in data centers that operators are doing for virtualizing services or even Virtual Network Functions (VNFs).

The first IP point of the operator's network is the BNG (Figure 4.8). This equipment is redundantly deployed for each 32K to 96K users, typically. The CDN of the operators are limited by this fact, since the video servers cannot be closer to the end user. However, the video servers can be placed in the access routers, transit routers or even at the interconnection level. If there were national CDN points this will lead on a high utilization of the video platform, since all users would access to the same point, thus statistically using the resources more often. However, each flow that is generated in this national video server would be transmitted through the whole national network. As these flows are unicast for the VoD or Time Shifted services, the overhead in the network is massive. On the other hand, the video servers can be deployed at the BRAS location, minimizing the network infrastructure, but increasing the video platform costs as the number of locations increases. Moreover, the dimensioning and caching is not so efficient as the number of customers using these video servers is smaller.

Figure 4.8: vCDN case study.

4.6 Application-centric in-operation network planning

Current transport networks are statically configured and managed, because they experience a rather limited traffic dynamicity. This leads to long planning cycles to upgrade the network and prepare it for the next planning period. This plan procedure aims that the network can support the forecast traffic and deal with failure scenarios, thus adding extra capacity and increasing network expenditures.

The second drawback of current static procedure is that the results from network capacity planning are manually deployed in the network, which limits the network agility. The main reason for this is that current provisioning systems are not always deployed as the number of configurations in IP/optical backbone networks is relatively small. However, on a scenario where lightpath provisioning can be automated, network resources can be made available by reconfiguring and/or re-optimising the network on-demand and in real-time. The authors in [VEL14] proposed this term of in-operation network planning. The main idea of in-operation network planning is to take advantage of novel network reconfiguration capabilities and new network management architectures to perform in-operation planning, aiming at reducing network CAPEX by minimising the over-provisioning required in today's static network environments.

The overall framework architecture of a statically configured network and a network that supports in-operation planning is shown in Figure 4.9. The key differentiation for the adoption of the in-operation planning approach is in the undertaken operations of the network provisioning system, which should now facilitate an in-operation (i.e. dynamic and real time) planning tool that interacts directly with the data and control planes. The adoption of the SDN framework with the north and south bound interfaces supports the realization of this concept in a multi-service and multi-vendor environment.

Figure 4.9: Evolution towards in-operations planning.

Within ACINO the in-operation planning concept is extended and includes application awareness. This denotes that overall planning of the resources is not performed solely for the optical infrastructure considering the aggregated data from the upper layer, but on a ‘per application demand’ basis considering both the IP and Optical layer resources. Figure 4.10 summarizes the original multi-layer planning approaches and also presents the ACINO dynamic multi-layer approach, which is defined in WP3 of this project. In this approach the incoming requests are classified in a sense that they generate different service requirements to the network which translate to different use of the available resources. These requirements are evaluated in real-time providing the optimal routing through IP and optical domain or establishing new IP or/and optical lightpaths if this is required.

Figure 4.10: Application oriented planning process.

The specific case study described above aims at integrating the ACINO application awareness concept with the in-operation planning concept. The dynamic provision of resources for different types of applications is enabled and will be studied for a set of service requirements set by the applications. It is of particular interest

to examine the dynamic behaviour of the network when applications with variable bandwidth characteristics are accommodated, while also examine the required adaptation time for dynamic re-optimization.

5 Reference Network

This section provides details about the reference network models adopted in ACINO to accurately represent a multi-layer (IP and Optical layer) infrastructure. The first part defines the main elements of the network architecture in IP metro core, metro and access network segments. The Spanish reference network that is adopted for the networking studies is described in the second part. Emphasis is given on the Mobile Backhaul, IP layer and Optical layer infrastructure.

5.1 Reference network model and definitions

ACINO project covers multi-layer scenarios where there are packet and optical technologies. The network where the IP and optical technologies are in use, is deployed in most of the network operators, as the backbone network. However, the metropolitan and backhaul network is becoming more and more important in terms of optical deployments. The reference network will be explained in general terms while numbers will be given for the scenarios that cope with the project needs.

Figure 5.1 shows a network reference model with more important elements in the fixed network of operator's networks.

Figure 5.1: Network reference model.

5.1.1 IP network architecture

IP network is usually composed by four levels of routers:

- **Interconnection Routers (IR):** They are located at the top level of the IP network, in the backbone network. They are the interface between IP network and Internet/ISP providers. In the MPLS context they are PE (Provider Edge) routers.

- **Transit Routers (TR):** They are located after the IR routers and carry traffic to/from the IR routers. They are P routers that do not aggregate traffic, only sends traffic toward the intended destination.
- **Aggregation Routers (AR):** These routers aggregate the traffic from the different locations of the Metro network.
- **Broadband Remote Access Server (BRAS):** They are located at the bottom level of the IP network, and are connected to the Metro segment. BRAS routers implement IP functionalities, such as traffic classification, subscriber's credentials authentication, validation of users access policies, routing data to the respective destination, etc.

5.1.2 Metro architecture

Metro architecture is typically composed of two or three main levels of aggregation. Beginning at the bottom of the architecture, the components that can be found are:

- **Gateway Terminal (GWT):** Aggregates traffic from different base stations (BS), which aggregate traffic from mobile subscribers.
- **Distribution Switches (SWD):** Aggregates traffic from OLTs, DSLAMs and SWTs.
- **Concentration switches (SWC):** Compose the highest level of the Metro segment. The SWCs aggregate traffic from the lower metro levels. They are also connected to the lower level of the IP segment (BRAS) for the fixes traffic.

5.1.3 Access network

The access network contains two main technologies for fixed technologies:

- **Digital Subscriber Line Access Multiplexer (DSLAM):** Aggregates the digital data coming from a number of DSL subscribers onto a single high-capacity uplink to the Internet Service Provider.
- **Optical Line Terminal (OLT):** Aggregates traffic from optical fiber users into a single high-capacity uplink to the Internet Service Provider.

It is worth mentioning that mobile access is also a third network, but in terms of high bandwidth that will impact the core network are minimum if they are compared with fixed access in most of the network operators.

5.2 Spanish Reference Network

5.2.1 Network evolution KPIs

During the last two years, as seen in Figure 5.2, Telefonica has observed that the number of customers has not increased as fast as it used to in Spain. There are two main reasons: the economic crisis and the competition. Both factors have pushed Telefonica to do a huge investment in fiber infrastructure in order to speed up the deployment and increase the quality of the access portfolio. This factor has clearly impacted the fiber access evolution in Spain (Figure 5.3), where the ‘million users’ goal was exceeded in 2014.

Figure 5.2: Thousands of broadband (xDSL and FTTH) users of Telefonica in Spain.

Figure 5.3: Thousands of FTTH users of Telefonica in Spain.

The access profile in Spain is shown in

Table 5-1. If we pondered such table with a medium bandwidth per segment, we can see that the average bandwidth is 37Mbps. Thus is much higher than it used to be in Spain in the last years.

Table 5-1: Access profile in Spain.

Access Profiles	
< 2 Mbps	0,7%

>= 2 Mbps < 10 Mbps	7,0%
>= 10 Mbps < 30 Mbps	71,1%
>= 30 Mbps < 50 Mbps	4,6%
>= 50 Mbps	16,6%

In order to increase the users' churn, Telefonica has carried out the acquisition of the content provider, Canal+ to increase its content offer. The name of the service is Movistar+. The IPTV service was provided by Telefonica since few years, but this acquisition allows Telefonica to offer multiple TV shows and movies titles to the end users. This focus on the TV content has boosted the number of Pay TV subscribers as shown in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: Thousands of Pay TV users of Telefonica in Spain.

Telefonica's customers in Spain can see multicast IP TV traffic in Standard and High Definition quality. Users can also subscribe to VoD services (TV shows and/or Movies) as well as recording and Time Shifted (TS) services. Recordings allow the customer to save a content that he is willing to see later. On the other hand, TS service is provided when the user sees a program that has already been displayed and he wants to see it from the beginning. VoD, recordings as well as TS services are unicast videos. Table 5-2 shows the number of channels in Movistar+ in Standard and High Definition for live TV, thus is multicast traffic.

Table 5-2: Number of channels for basic and premium Movistar+ customers.

	Movistar+	
Basic	SD	55
	HD	43
Premium	SD	55
	HD	60

To conclude, let us highlight, where the video is injected on the network. There is a hierarchical Content Delivery Network (CDN) platform that sends the content from the content servers to the replica sites using multicast flows for the IPTV traffic. The replica sites store the on-demand content (VoD, recordings and TS)

and forward the multi-cast video to the end users. These replica servers are located in the aggregation routers of the network. The end user selects the video he wants to see and advertise the DSLAM or OLT about the multicast flow he wants to subscribe to or the unicast flows that should be streamed.

5.2.2 Mobile Backhaul/Metro scenario

Common transmission deployments rely on technologies with moderate performance in terms of reach and overall capacity for metro scenarios. So far, the most common architecture to deploy metropolitan networks is not supported on an optical transmission layer. The metro/MBH area is composed by SWCs, SWDs and SWTs as stated in the previous sections.

Multi-layer architectural alternatives

In the source, destination and each intermediate node the information is aggregated in the electrical domain and transmitted via grey interfaces. An example of these networks with a ring structure is depicted in Figure 5.5. In this network, traffic from SWDs (20G) is aggregated in each of the intermediate SWDs through its way to the SWCs. The ring in Figure 5.5 is dimensioned to support single failure, so the fiber between SWD₁ and SWC₁ has to support 60 G (20 G from SWD₁, 20 G from SWD₂ and 20 G from SWD₃, the two latter to support failure of the SWD₃-SWC₂ fiber). Although the capacity of the network can be upgraded using interfaces with higher performance (i.e. 100 G instead of 10 G ports), this architecture presents a number of limitations, regarding the computation capacity of the intermediate nodes and the number of fibers to be deployed or used.

Figure 5.5: Example of metro ring topology with no optical layer.

However, with the increment of the traffic demand in recent years, these architectures have to evolve to be efficient. One possibility would be to deploy new fibers from the SWDs to the SWCs, converting the physical topology from a ring to a star/tree topology, where each SWD has a direct fiber connection to each SWC using dark fiber (as it is depicted in Figure 5.6).

Figure 5.6: Physical topology for dark fiber deployments.

Other possibility relies on the use of WDM optical networks. In this sense, each SWD is logically connected to each SWC by means of a different wavelength. Thus, conforming a logical star/tree topology under a ring physical topology. Figure 5.7 shows the physical and logical topology of these WDM coloured networks. It can be seen that, using the same ring fiber infrastructure, the logical topology is a star with all SWDs connected directly to the SWCs.

Figure 5.7: Physical and logical topology for coloured ring deployments.

To deploy this type of networks, CWDM and DWDM can be used. In some cases, non-amplified structures based on CWDM buses or rings, with a limited number of channels can be enough. In other cases, metro performance DWDM rings enable coverage of the remaining network scenarios. Optical meshes are commonly restricted to densely populated areas, with higher needs of capacity and redundancy. In any case, optical nodes usually provide no reconfiguration capabilities (are based on Fixed OADM) or control plane driven restoration. Data equipment for this approach is connected to the “client side” of CWDM or DWDM transponders by means of “grey” interfaces. Then, the “coloured” optical signals can be amplified or not depending on their nature (DWDM vs CWDM) and filtered at the optical nodes. However, this architecture has the inconvenience of deploying new optical nodes with active equipment and an additional network management system for the optical layer. An example of this architecture can be seen in Figure 5.8.

Figure 5.8: Example of CWDM/DWDM metro architecture with optical nodes.

An alternative simpler approach to deploy logical trees, can be based on the direct use of coloured interfaces at the data equipment, using simple passive filters for the sake of adding/dropping signals (optical passive deployment). Even though there is a possibility to amplify the DWDM signals coming from the data nodes. This would imply the maintenance and control of an active additional equipment, i.e. to deploy a “reduced” optical node (with no transponders) collocated with every router/switch to compensate the filtering and transmission loss. It would be pretty convenient to leverage the specific parameters found in the metro environment (few nodes to be traversed from origin to destination, short link distances, low number of channels) to avoid amplification and consider a simple and inexpensive architecture based on the use of end-to-end optical paths established over a set of passive WDM filters.

The architecture allows considering logical star topologies (with lightpaths to headend nodes using separate wavelengths) over a shared ring based fiber deployment. This will be feasible over metro scenarios subject to some restrictions, as coloured interfaces will have an operating margin in terms of sensitivity. This margin will translate into a maximum level of fiber+filtering compound losses (attenuation and insertion at every filter) that ensures an adequate power level at the ends of every light path. The maximum number of nodes and fiber length of a feasible structure will depend on the number of WDM channels (the lower the better), the filter characteristics in terms of loss and the fiber quality and span lengths. An example of this architecture can be seen in.

Figure 5.9: Example of passive optical metro architecture.

Finally another approach consists of using OTN (Figure 5.10). Contrary to the second approach, where one wavelength is used to transmit data of just one SWD, the use of OTN allows the switching of sub-wavelength bitrates. This enables for example to add/drop at the OTN layer (without aggregating the traffic at higher levels) portions of a 100 G stream, enabling the use of 10 G interfaces at the Ethernet level. For example, in Figure 5.10, SWD₂ transmits 60 Gbps in a stream of 100 G in the WDM layer (60% of occupation of the wavelength). This flow is aggregated in its way to SWC₁ with a flow of 30 Gbps coming from SWD₁, increasing the occupation of the wavelength to the 90%. As it can be observed, both flows are switched at OTN layer.

Figure 5.10: Metro network with OTN layer.

The node architecture adds an OTN chassis, which includes the switch matrix, the tributary cards, which convert the client/Ethernet signals to Optical Channel Data Units (ODUs) and the line cards. Moreover, we have assumed that line cards include the colored transceiver.

Scenario for the analysis

Specifically, a ring topology with 2 SWC sites and 5 SWDs is considered. The SWDs are distributed in two concentric rings (Figure 5.11), with 2 SWCs and 2 SWDs in one ring, and the 2 SWCs and 3 SWDs in another ring.

Figure 5.11: Reference network scenario.

Regarding the traffic on the metro network, it has been assumed that each SWD on average generates from 1 Gb/s to 80 Gb/s. The total average network load is at 400 Gb/s. Moreover, to dimension the network and determine the number of line cards and transceivers, the network has been designed to support simple failure of links and nodes. Also, the maximum link occupation bound has been set to the 80%.

In a metro environment like the one described above, amplification is not needed. Thus, it can be assumed that all fiber connections have the same cost. A mean distance of 20 km, an intermediate value for metro networks is realistic for urban scenarios. Low aggregation metro segment is a ring topology with 2 SWDs and 10 SWTs, with a fiber length between the nodes with a mean of 4 Km, so the distance for any optical path does not exceed 40 Km. Based on Telefonica internal information, this ring is feasible for the passive solution using filters with low pass-through insertion losses.

Figure 5.12: Lower metro ring topology.

5.2.3 IP layer

The aggregation routers and the transit routers are connected via regional IP networks. Each regional IP network has a pair of transit routers (for example TR1 and TR2 topology), with different number of aggregation nodes. Each aggregation router is connected to two transit routers as shown in Figure 5.13. The aim of this double connection is to have single failure protection. This does not mean that the link is unused, but that the routers are load balancing the traffic using Equal Cost Multi-Path (ECMP).

Figure 5.13: Access and transit router interconnection.

The transit routers are split in even and odd routers and there are seven regions. Two routers form a pair which do not exchange traffic between them. For instance, routers TR1 and TR2 are a pair and they do not exchange traffic. These routers received the same amount of traffic as they are feed by the same access routers as explained before. However, each TR pair has a different number of access routers, as shown in Table 5-3.

Table 5-3: Regions, and number of aggregation routers.

Region ID	Transit 1	Transit 2	# aggregation routers
1	1	2	29
2	9	10	12
3	5	6	30
4	3	4	28
5	11	12	18
6	7	8	8
7	13	14	23

The transit routers are connected as shown in Figure 5.14. Not all transit routers are connected among them, because there is not enough traffic today. Based on current traffic pattern, the transit and interconnection routers all transit routers send traffic to the interconnection routers.

Figure 5.14: Transit routers topology and location of interconnection routers.

5.2.4 Optical layer infrastructure

Telefónica’s transport network is based on a hierarchical structure with five meshed regional domains and one “express” national domain. Intra-regional communications make use of resources within the specific region, while inter-regional communications may be established using some inter-regional links or through a dedicated (express) national domain, whose ROADMs (reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexer) are collocated with some selected ROADMs at each regional domain. As a starting point, we consider for the Telefónica network model a “Broadcast and Select architecture”, with LCoS (liquid crystal on silicon) based ROADMs with up to 9 degrees and cascaded Nx1 WSS blocks for the colourless tributary side at Rx. In addition as a transport technology, uncompensated schemes are generally deployed (regional and national domains), so that only coherent technologies are considered in the network. Telefónica network topology is shown in Figure 5.15 and Figure 5.16. Figure 5.16 shows the mapping between the Transit and Interconnection Routers with the optical nodes.

Figure 5.15: Telefónica reference network. Regional domains.

Figure 5.16: Telefónica reference network. National domain.

SMF fibre is used on all the network segments and links. It is assumed that the oldest fibre layouts have been renewed and the fibre links are in a relatively good state. The fibre used is SMF G.652-D with the following physical characteristics:

- Chromatic dispersion at 1550nm: 16.5 ps/nm.km
- Chromatic dispersion slope at 1550 nm: 0.057ps/nm².km
- Attenuation coefficient: following a normal distribution with mean 0.22 dB/km and standard deviation of 0.0068 dB/km. Minimum/maximum attenuation on a fibre segment: 0.1997/0.2371 dB/km.
- PMD coefficient: the maximum value for a fibre link is 0.3995 ps/sqr(km), while the minimum is 0.0213 ps/sqr(km).

An Excel spreadsheet file with link and amplifier details for the regional domains and for the national domain is provided.

The reference network presents the transport framework for national and regional networks. There are several optical technologies that can be deployed in this reference network (for instance, OTN, WSON, SSON or SDM). The aim of ACINO is not to study a specific optical technology, but to assess in each study the best technology for the selected scenario. For metro networks, OTN is the best candidate technology as it allows a lower granularity, which can be used to map applications easily while SDM is the candidate technology for high bandwidth backbones.

6 Network cost model and preliminary evaluations

This section presents the cost model that will be used for the techno-economic evaluation of ACINO solutions. Based on the defined cost model, the ACINO cost module is implemented within the Net2Plan evaluation platform that is developed under WP3. Some preliminary evaluation results are presented to provide a reference indication for the cost savings that can be achieved with the use of application aware routing in multi-layer IP-Optical networks.

6.1 ACINO cost model description

ACINO consortium has full access to 3 complete cost models with data for both IP and Optical layer equipment including also in some cases different technology approaches. These are:

- a. the ICT FP7 project STRONGEST cost model extracted and studied in 2013,
- b. the ICT FP7 project FOX-C cost model extracted and studied in 2015 and
- c. a cost model extracted by the list prices offered by one of the largest system vendors Cisco.

The goal for the extraction of the ACINO cost model is to use all the previous models and verify (to the extent that this is possible) an accurate and realistic model that includes the equipment costs of the most advanced solutions available in market today, while also reference to negotiated cost values, (offered typically to operators) rather than list prices.

6.1.1 Previous models and related data

The available cost data from the 3 models mentioned above are listed in the following paragraphs

STRONGEST cost model

The STRONGEST cost model has been presented in [RAM13] and the tables below summarize the considered costs which are normalized to the cost of a 10Gb/s transponder.

For the upper layer, the MPLS-TP equipment from [RAM13] has been considered for metro networks (chassis, line cards and pluggables) and for the lower layer, the OTN equipment. Moreover, a FOADM of 2 degree (cost equal to 5.2) has been considered.

Table 6-1: Metro Ethernet costs – ICT FP7 STRONGEST cost model [RAM13].

Metro Ethernet costs			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	
ME1	8	-	
ME2	16	2.47	
Cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
LC3	2	10	0.85

LC4	5	10	-
LC5	10	10	3.4
LC6	24	10	-
LC7	40	10	-
LC8	1	100	4.7
Grey Pluggables (short reach)			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]		Cost
XFP	10		0.1
CFP	100		1

Table 6-2: OTN costs – ICT FP7 STRONGEST cost model [RAM13].

OTN cost			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	SlotThroughput
Chassis_1	8	5	400
Line cards (including transceiver)			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
1x100	1	100	26
Tributary cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
8x1	8	1	-
24x1	48	1	3.04
2x10	2	10	-
4x10	4	10	-
8x10	40	10	6
1x100	1	100	12
Tributary pluggables			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	
SFP	1	0.02	
XFP	10	0.1	
CFP	100	1	
Switching matrix			
Type	Capacity	Cost	
	500G<x>1T	Included in chassis	

FOX-C cost model

FOX-C cost model has been obtained from [THO15]. In this case, the upper layer components are of IP layer, and the lower layer of OTN. In this case, costs are normalized using the cost of a colored 10G transponder. Moreover, a ROADM of 2 degree (cost equal to 12.36) has been considered.

Table below summarizes the costs considered:

Table 6-3: IP costs – ICT FP7 FOX-C cost model [THO15].

IP costs			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	
Router	16	1.62	
Cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
10x10	10	10	5.08
1x100	1	100	8.42
Pluggables grey short reach			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	
XFP	10	0.04	Short reach (m)
CFP	100	4.17	Short reach (m)

Table 6-4: OTN costs – ICT FP7 FOX-C cost model [THO15].

OTN cost			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	SlotThroughput
	16	10.15	50
	16	12.77	100
	32	17.47	50
	32	20.91	100
Line cards (transceiver included)			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
1x100	1	100	9.59
Tributary cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
10x10	10	10	2.65
1x100	1	100	5.56
Tributary pluggables			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	

	10	0	Included
	100	4.17	
Switching matrix			
Type	Capacity	Cost	
		0	Included in OTN Chassis

Cisco cost model

Data has been obtained from “Cisco GPL 2016” public list prices (available at <http://ciscoprice.com/>). The selected equipment is for a metro network. Specifically, the equipment and cost is shown in the table below. Moreover, a ROADM of 2 degree (cost equal to 3.36) has been considered.

Table 6-5: Metro Ethernet costs – CISCO.

ME costs			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	
ASR-9006-DC-V2	6	0.43902439	ASR 9006 DC Chassis with PEM Version 2
ASR-9010-DC-V2	10	0.590243902	ASR 9010 DC Chassis with PEM Version 2
Cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
A9K2G20GE-B	2	10	3.170731707
A9K-4T-B	4	10	3.170731707
A9K-8T-B	8	10	6.341463415
A9K-16T/8-B	16	10	8.292682927
LC7	40	10	
A9K-1X100GE-TR	1	100	7.317073171
Pluggables (grey short reach)			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	
XFP-10G-MM-SR	10	0.097317073	Short reach (m)
CFP-100G-SR10	100	0.780243902	Short reach (m)

Table 6-6: OTN costs – CISCO.

OTN cost			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	SlotThroughput

NCS4009-FC-S=	9	1.097560976	100
Line cards (no transceiver included)			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
NCS4K-2H-O-K	2	100	4.682926829
Line cards pluggables			
Type	Capacity (Gbps)	Average Cost	
CPAK-100G-LR4	100	\$ 40000.00	
Tributary cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
8x1	8	1	
24x1	24	1	2.341463415
2x10	2	10	
4x10	4	10	2.341463415
8x10	8	10	
1x100	1	100	
Tributary pluggables			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	
	1		
	10	0.072926829	
	100		
Switching matrix			
Type	Capacity	Cost	
	500G<x>1T	0	

6.1.2 Cost model comparison and validation

A simulation set-up has been used similar to one presented in section 5.2 with the goal to compare the different cost models and examine their trend as traffic grows. The purpose is to decide which models are better describing the multi-layer resource allocation cost and therefore which one to adopt for the ACINO project. The simulations have been done in a metropolitan network considering IP/Ethernet+OTN layers. The cost models under comparison are those summarised in the previous section.

Simulation scenario

Regarding the traffic on the metro network, it has been assumed here that each SWD in mean generates from 1 Gb/s to 140 Gb/s. Moreover, to dimension the network and determine the number of line cards and transceivers, the network has been designed to support single failure of links and nodes. Also, a maximum link occupation limit has been set to the 80%.

Figure 6.1: Network scenario of the study.

Node model

As it can be seen in Figure 6.2, the complete node model is composed of two layers, IP/Ethernet and OTN layers. In the IP/Ethernet layer, it has been considered the chassis, line cards and short pluggables to connect with the OTN layer.

OTN layer is composed by tributary cards and tributary ports which interconnects the IP/Ethernet and OTN layers, the chassis (which includes the switching matrix) and the line cards with the transponders included.

Figure 6.2: Node model.

Cost Analysis

The main objective of this study is not to do a comparison in terms of real costs, but to identify the trend. That is, in order to determine the cost model that best reflects the real cost, we are not considering the total prices but the trend of increment. In this way, we can in some way remove the differences in the models obtained by different discounts offered and negotiation steps.

The results of the comparisons of the cost models considered are shown in Figure 6.3. As it can be observed, FOX-C and Cisco cost models follow the same trend, whereas STRONGEST model presents a greater slope.

Figure 6.3: Cost model comparison.

If we make that all curves start at the same point for the lowest traffic generated by subtracting the total cost when traffic is 0 for the lowest cost model (Figure 6.4), we can see that for low traffic, all models behaviour' is similar. On the other hand, for higher traffic, cost increase with traffic is higher in the STRONGEST model.

Figure 6.4: Cost model comparison when all curves star at the same point.

The conclusions are similar, FOX-C and Cisco cost models present a similar trend, whereas STRONGEST cost model has a different behaviour.

In order to quantify the similarity between models, we have done a linear regression and try to approximate each curve with a straight line with an equation of type $y = a \cdot x + b$, where the term a represents the slope and the term b the interception.

Figure 6.5 represents the each curve and its approximation, and the table below shows the results of the approximation of each curve (the slope and the interception).

Figure 6.5: Cost model linear approximations.

Table 6-7: Slope and interception values.

	STRONGEST	FOX-C	Cisco
Slope	6.7698	4.3311	4.5271
Interception	487.0699	592.7995	201.6734

As we have said before, this study is focused in the analysis of the trend, and not in the concrete values of cost. Therefore, the interception values are not considered and only the slope.

As it can be seen, both FOX-C and Cisco have similar slopes, (4.3 and 4.5), which means that the trend to the long term is similar. On the other hand, STRONGEST cost model has a slope of 6.7, which is significantly higher than the other two models.

Conclusion

Data from three different cost models were collected and presented. These refer to the cost of the required equipment for IP and OTN network layer. The STRONGEST cost model is dated back to 2012 and reported in [RAM13]. The FOX-C cost model is extracted in 2015 [THO15]. The FOX-C model refers to final costs obtained by an operator after several round of negotiations with vendors. The third model is the Cisco cost model and is extracted from current list prices available online.

Based on a networking study, the three cost models are compared in terms of cost scaling with respect to traffic load. These comparisons show that the FOX-C and Cisco models have almost the same trend, while the older STRONGEST model no longer represents accurately the cost relation. This is attributed to the changes of the relative cost between IP and Optical (i.e. OTN) components over the last years, but also to fact that Cisco and FOX-C models present currently a higher granularity in the line cards, which make the cost of networks with higher traffic lower.

The ACINO consortium decided to adopt the FOX-C cost model for the relative studies in WP2. The model follows accurately the current trend of the Cisco cost model, while it is also more realistic (in terms of absolute cost values), since it is based on data provided by a telecom operator after negotiations.

6.1.3 ACINO cost model for IP layer

The cost model for the IP layer has three major cost items, namely IP chassis, linecards and short reach transceivers. From the number of links served, the required number of transceivers is calculated for each bit rate supported. This number is then used to estimate the number and kind of linecards required. Then an appropriate chassis that can house all linecards is selected. An important issue to note is that this calculation is used only for the transport side of the network, ignoring the connection to the metro/access network, since the latter is assumed to be identical between the different scenarios studied.

The cost mode selected has just a single router configuration with 16 slots. Since we need more than this for certain configurations, an estimate was made for additional configurations, based on the cost scaling used in the model in [RAM13] (Table 6-1). The full set of values used is shown in Table 6-8.

Table 6-8: IP cost values used.

IP costs – ACINO			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	
Router	16	1.62	
Router	32	4.860	Scaling from [RAM13]
Router	48	7.290	Scaling from [RAM13]
Router	64	9.720	Scaling from [RAM13]
Router	80	12.150	Scaling from [RAM13]
Router	96	14.580	Scaling from [RAM13]
Router	112	17.010	Scaling from [RAM13]
Router	128	19.440	Scaling from [RAM13]
Router	144	21.870	Scaling from [RAM13]
Cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
10x10	10	10	5.08
1x100	1	100	8.42
Pluggables (grey - short reach)			

Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	
XFP	10	0.04	Short reach (m)
CFP	100	4.17	Short reach (m)

6.1.4 ACINO cost model for Optical layer

In the OTN cost model there are five major cost items, the chassis, the line cards, the tributary cards, the tributary pluggables and the long reach transponders. The assumption here is that for each long reach transponder there is an equivalent tributary pluggable to connect to a grey IP layer transceiver, and that for each line card there is the equivalent tributary card.

In the cost model of [THO15], no value is provided for the 10 port linecard for 10 Gb/s transponders. This is estimated to be equal to the tributary card with the same size, but without the transponders. The full set of values used is shown in Table 6-9.

Table 6-9: OTN cost values used.

OTN cost – ACINO			
Chassis			
Type	Num. Slots	Cost	Slot Throughput
	16	12.77	100
	32	20.91	100
Line cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
10x10	10	10	2.65 (estimated)
1x100	1	100	9.59 (transceiver included)
Tributary cards			
Type	Num. Ports	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost
10x10	10	10	2.65
1x100	1	100	5.56
Tributary pluggables			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	
	10	0	Included
	100	4.17	
Long reach pluggables			
Type	Capacity [Gbps]	Cost	
	10	1	
	100	0	Included

6.2 Cost module Implementation in ACINO resource allocation framework

The goal for the implemented cost module is to be used as a stand-alone cost evaluation tool when different resource allocation and optimization scenarios are evaluated. Therefore, the module must be independent of the allocation and optimization processes and be able to provide the overall network cost, (ideally also other detailed cost statistics), on demand. For this reason, the ACINO cost module has been implemented as separate module on top of the ACINO resource allocation framework, implemented on the Net2Plan platform. A detailed description of the module is provided in the following sub-sections.

6.2.1 Overview of ACINO framework and implementation remarks

As described in more detail in deliverable D3.4, the ACINO resource allocation and optimization framework comprises three modules: IP Provisioning (IPP-M), IP Optimization (IP-OPT-M), and Optical Provisioning (OPP-M). IPP-M tries to satisfy demands by using available resources at the IP layer only. IP-OPT-M changes the existing routes in the IP. OPP-M adds new lightpaths, which are then used as IP links.

In brief, when a service request is received, an effort is made to set up an application-aware path by using IPP-M. The path is then requested from the IP controller, unless there have been too many successful accommodations using IPP-M. In that case, or if IPP-M fails, IP-OPT-M is called to rearrange the IP layer connections to free up unneeded transceivers. This IP layer re-optimization can reduce power, or optimize the network for another objective. Otherwise, if IPP-M fails, the request is passed to IP-OPT-M, and if that fails, to OPP-M, which calls IP-OPT-M to select the paths for new optical connections.

In this framework, there are currently two uses of the cost model:

- The overall network cost is computed automatically during the framework operation in order to be reported
- A detailed report can be provided on demand, accounting for the cost items calculated per node in the network.

A more detailed view of the cost model operation follows.

6.2.2 Cost module implementation details

In order to keep the cost model configurable without sacrificing usability, the choice was made to use .xls files to input the various cost items. This provides an easy way to modify the cost parameters without complicating the Net2Plan user interface. This however necessitates the use of external libraries that must be made available to Net2Plan during execution of the code. Two such libraries are needed, the “Java Excel API”² and “Apache POI”³. Net2Plan provides an easy way to add external libraries using the “Classpath editor” accessible from the file menu. The cost model checks that the libraries are available and gives an error message to the user if not.

² <http://jexcelapi.sourceforge.net/>

³ <https://poi.apache.org/>

When the cost model is used as part of the online (dynamic) evaluation scenario, only the total cost value for the whole network is calculated. A configuration parameter “costModelFrequency” has been added that allows to specify how often to evaluate the cost during the online evaluation process. In this case the parameter defines after how many incoming allocation demands the cost will be calculated. This allows to save significant simulation time by using a longer calculation frequency. The same parameter can be used to completely disable the cost model by using the value “-1”.

Finally, the cost model can be used to generate a detailed report of the cost items per node in the network. This is accessed through the “View reports” tab of Net2Plan and is usable both in online simulation mode and in offline mode. Figure 6.6 (left) shows the detailed cost report for one scenario, as viewed in Net2Plan. In addition, the detailed cost report can be saved as an .html file and viewed in a browser Figure 6.6 (right)

Figure 6.6: Cost report as seen in Net2Plan(left) and in browser (right).

6.3 Preliminary results

A preliminary cost evaluation study has been performed and presented in this subsection. The purpose of this study is to provide an initial evaluation on the cost benefits that can be achieved by adopting the application aware resource allocation concept in a multi-layer core network environment. The work presents also the methodology that is adopted for comparing the ACINO approach to a non-application aware multi-layer approach, as well as approaches that skip the calculation intensive optimization process.

The results have been obtained by using the ACINO resource allocation and optimization framework implemented in Net2Plan simulation platform. The cost module has been added to this framework and was activated, in order to provide continuous cost estimation update after each allocation of a demand in a dynamic scenario. Details about the implemented framework and modules are provided in sections 2 and 3 of deliverable D3.4.

6.3.1 Cost comparison methodology

The cost comparison methodology is based in the general comparison methodology defined in sub-section 4.1.3 of deliverable D3.4. Here, we define 6 comparison cases for the application- and non-application-aware cases as shown in Figure 6.7. The ACINO framework is represented by A2, whereas the non-ACINO (i.e. multi-layer but non-application-aware) framework by B2. By disabling the optimization feature in each of the aforementioned cases, we define the simple application-aware and simple non-application-aware cases A1 and B1 respectively. The ‘global optimization’ cases are non-practical cases and defined only as benchmarking cases in order to identify the (almost) best allocation of resources. Therefore, A3 and B3 cases are not used for the cost comparison studies.

Figure 6.7: Evaluation options for the application and non-application aware cases.

Based on the above, the following comparison cases are valid and used in our studies:

- A2-B2 comparison: This is the basic comparison between the ACINO and non-ACINO case. Application awareness is expected to add restrictions on the use of resources which may affect the cost. In terms of overall cost, this comparison will show the additional cost needed in order to support application awareness.

- A2-A1 comparison: This comparison evaluates the added benefit by using the resource optimization process. The simple application-aware allocation of resources can be a costly process since any restrictions are translated to additional use of resources. The value of ACINO re-optimization process can be evaluated by calculating the achievable network cost reduction
- A2-(B2)-B1: B1 represents the simplest (multi-layer) allocation process and is the benchmarking for our cost studies. The application-awareness and optimization processes that are added for A2 and B2 cases increase the complexity but effectively are able to reduce the overall network cost.

The comparisons above provide an estimation of the overall network cost for each case, but avoid taking into consideration any performance related metric. A cost comparison can be valid in absolute cost terms, if one considers simply the achievable cost benefits or loss with respect only to the required network resources, but without considering the added benefit in terms of service guaranties or customer satisfaction or other application/service related metric. In order to have a fairer comparison, one should also take into consideration the service request violation and the connection establishment blocking metrics for the different cases. (See definition of metrics in subsection 4.1.2 of D3.4).

One way to evaluate the cost benefit of application awareness for ACINO (A2) is to estimate the cost penalty of the service request violations (or equally the inability to provide guaranteed service requests) in the non-ACINO case (B2). However, such an evaluation requires data from marketing and business development sectors which is not easily available.

An alternative way that is considered in our evaluation methodology is the following. In ACINO case (A2) if there are no network resources to guarantee the requested service requirements for a certain demand, then this demand is blocked. In the non-ACINO case the application aware policies are not applied and therefore the same demand can be allocated over any path in the network. If application awareness was active then this path would violate the service requirements. This is marked as service request violation for the relative B2 case demands. Therefore, a fair comparison can be made between A2 and B2 cases if the number of blocked demands in A2 case is equal to the number of violated plus blocked demands in B2 case and for the same overall load. In order to increase the blocking in A2 case, the available network resources must be reduced (i.e. we can set an upper limit in the number of available optical paths per link). The reduced number of resources represents a network cost value that could safely represent the cost penalty due to lack of service guaranties in the non-ACINO case. Evidently, this approach provides only resource-related cost estimations and does not consider the value of the services and the offered guaranties.

6.3.2 Assumed application driven resource allocation scenario and characteristics

A broad performance evaluation of different application demands and types is carried out in sections 4.3 and 4.4 of deliverable D3.4. Based on the acquired knowledge from these studies we derive a simple 2-class application aware scenario for the preliminary cost studies presented below.

This scenario assumes that 50% of the generated traffic services require low latency and high availability, while the rest 50% has no specific service requirements (i.e. best effort traffic). This case is chosen because it results in average service request violation values for B2 case and very small connection blocking

probabilities for the ACINO case (A2). The generated demands in the IP layer range uniformly between 10Gb/s and 100Gb/s and are aggregated and allocated over 100Gb/s wavelength channels. The network load is derived from the average traffic load data of 2016 and is scaled up to the estimated average load for 2020 assuming an annual traffic increase by 30%.

Moreover, the studies focus on different traffic demand loads ranging from half up to 4 times the reference load for 2020. The following table (Table 6-10) shows the related performance metric results for all the studied cases.

Table 6-10: Performance values for different cases.

		Load x0.5	Load x1	Load x2	Load x4
A2 (ACINO)	Service request violation	0	0	0	0
	Connection blocking probability	0.09%	0.12%	0.13%	0.18%
B2 (non-ACINO)	Service request violation	11.82%	11.74%	12.67%	12.29%
	Connection blocking probability	0	0	0	0
A1 (app-aware, non-opt)	Service request violation	0	0	0	0
	Connection blocking probability	0.14%	0.14%	0.19%	0.22%
B1 (app-unaware, non-opt)	Service request violation	9.99%	9.33%	8.65%	8.24%
	Connection blocking probability	0	0	0	0

6.3.3 Cost evaluation results and discussion

We run network simulations for all four cases mentioned above, using the 2-layer (IP and Optical) national Spanish network of Telefonica. See Figure 5.14 for the reference IP network topology and Figure 5.16 for the optical layer topology. Each case has also been studied for four different traffic load conditions.

The total network cost and the number of IP resources (links) over the simulation time of 10.000 random demands are depicted in Figure 6.8. The initialization time period, which is around 10% of the total simulation time, is the network initialization phase and is ignored in all the measurements and collection of statistics that follow. We observe here that the IP link variation patterns over the simulation time are also repeated in the related variations of cost for all cases. This is expected since the number of IP links defines the number of required transceiver line cards which in turn have a major impact in the overall cost of the network. Also in the same figure we see that the non-optimised (i.e. simple allocation) cases A1 and B1 have a higher network cost than the ACINO (A2) and non-ACINO (B2) cases at each point of the simulation time. It is noted that in all cases the same traffic/event generation pattern is used by using the same random seed number.

Figure 6.8: Total network cost and IP link variations over the simulation time.

The same simulation results as those presented in Figure 6.8 have also been collected for different traffic loads. From these results, we extract the key cost statistics (mean, maximum and minimum cost) for all cases and present them in Figure 6.9.

As the load doubles the overall network cost increases significantly. The cost increase between the reference load and half the reference load is around 66% ($\pm 2.5\%$) for all cases. As the load doubles with respect to the reference load, the cost increases by 74% ($\pm 3\%$).

Figure 6.9: Overall network cost for different load values.

The non-ACINO application unaware (B2) case has the smallest overall network cost. This is because it optimizes the allocated resources while also there are no restrictions in the use of the available network resources. The ACINO case (A2) pays a small cost penalty with respect to non-ACINO (B2) case, in its effort to allocate the resources and satisfy the service requirements of the demands. The non-optimized application aware case (A1) has the highest cost due to the lack of resource optimization. Equally, the non-optimized version of the application unaware case (B1) shows a similar increased cost.

The cost difference between A2-B2 and A1-B1 is almost the same at different load values and is about 5% or less with respect to the average cost. This cost difference shows the additional cost required in terms of network resources in order to support application awareness.

The cost difference between A2-A1 and B2-B1 is also similar at different load values and is about 16% with respect to the average cost. In this case the cost difference shows the added cost benefit due to the use of the optimization processes implemented by the IP-OPT module.

Focusing next only on the ACINO case (A2), the overall network cost difference between A2 and all other cases at different load values is shown in Table 6-11. Also here we show the cost difference bot with respect to the average and the maximum cost value. One may argue that a reference to a maximum cost value is more accurate since resources must be overprovisioned in order to guaranty the accommodation of all demands as the traffic load varies over time. In this table, a positive cost difference shows that ACINO requires a higher cost, while the opposite is true for a negative value.

The cost difference between ACINO and non-ACINO is about 5% at the reference load and decreases as the load increases down to 3.2% cost difference. The same trend is also observed with respect to the maximum cost value starting though from almost 8% cost difference at the reference load value and dropping to 4.6% difference at higher load. The cost benefit of ACINO compared to the non-optimized version of ACINO (A1) is more pronounced and goes beyond 15% in terms of the average load while it varies between 9.5% and 16.7% with respect to the maximum cost values.

Table 6-11: Cost difference of ACINO (A2) with respect to other cases.

	With respect to average cost values				With respect to maximum cost values			
	Load x0.5	Load x1	Load x2	Load x4	Load x0.5	Load x1	Load 2	Load x4
B2 (non-ACINO)	4.27%	5.15%	4.83%	3.26%	1.40%	8.27%	5.25%	4.61%
A1 (app-aware, non-opt)	-16.43%	-16.99%	-16.39%	-15.33%	-13.21%	-9.51%	-16.70%	-15.58%
B1 (app-unaware, non-opt)	-9.87%	-12.43%	-13.28%	-10.24%	-5.77%	-4.82%	-8.23%	-8.26%

It was shown above that the addition of the application awareness concept by ACINO results in a small increase of about 5% or less in the required network resources in order to be supported. On the other hand

the service requirements of certain demands can be fully satisfied with ACINO approach, while using the most cost efficient non-ACINO approach, a service request violation of around 11.7% is observed (see Table 6-10). As it is mentioned in the last paragraph of sub-section 6.3.1, it is rather difficult to evaluate the actual cost benefits due to the offered service availability. However we may use the rational developed in that paragraph to evaluate the cost benefit in terms only of network resources if ACINO has the same performance outcome like the non-ACINO case.

In order to do this we have limited the optical layer resources to 9 channels first and 8 channels later. This limitation increases the percentage of blocked connections in ACINO case (A2) as it is unable to find resources that satisfy the requested service requirements. The results of this final study are shown in Table 6-12. By setting an upper limit of 8channels per link a connection blocking of 12.7% is observed which is comparable to the 11.7% of service request violation in B2 case. Comparing the original ACINO case with the one with limited resources we observe 11.2% of cost reduction in the average number of the overall network resources which increases to 18.6% with respect to the maximum cost values. These percentages of the equivalent cost benefits in terms of network resources are much larger than the percentages of the additionally required cost to support application awareness features, showing that overall ACINO offers a more cost effective solution. The cost benefits can be further highlighted if we consider the added value in terms of the offered service availability and connection guaranties for specific end users.

Table 6-12: Performance characteristics and cost difference of the reference ACINO case and ACINO case applied over network with limited optical resources per link (i.e. resulting in high blocking probability).

	Blocked connections	Cost difference w.r.t A2 (average values)	Cost difference w.r.t A2 (maximum values)
Ref. ACINO (A2)	0.12%	-	-
ACINO over max of 9ch per link*	7.38%	-4.83%	-9.60%
ACINO over max of 8ch per link*	12.73%	-11.17%	-18.60%

*Service request violation for B2 (non-ACINO) case is 11.7%

6.3.4 Main conclusion and remarks

In this preliminary cost evaluation study we have examined a representative and simple application aware scenario that mixes sensitive traffic with best effort traffic. The evaluation has focused on:

- a) the added cost required due to the use of application awareness,
- b) the cost benefit that can be achieved due to resource optimization and
- c) the estimate of the cost benefit in terms of service provisioning and according to the related use of resources.

The introduction of application awareness in a multi-layer resource allocation framework (with the same resource optimization functions when application awareness is used or not), results in about 5% increase in

terms of average cost. This is due to the additional resources (i.e. optical and IP connections) required in order to satisfy the service requirements. The required added cost drops as the load increases, because the overall number of resources increases.

The developed resource optimization process is capable of reducing the number of required network resources, leading to an overall cost reduction by more than 15%. This is valid for both the application aware and unaware cases.

The application unaware and optimized case leads to a certain percentage of service violations for the specific scenario examined here. If the application aware and optimized case (i.e. the ACINO case) applies over a network of limited resources, then effectively the blocking rate will increase. The cost difference between the network with limited resources, and the original network used for the application unaware case is about 12%. One can claim that this is the actual cost benefit of ACINO in comparison to a non-ACINO case (both being optimised in terms of resource usage), in terms only of the required network resources. For an accurate comparison the evaluation also of the service availability cost must be estimated, which is rather complex to be evaluated, as it requires knowledge from the sales and marketing sectors.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACINO	Application Centric IP/Optical Networks Orchestration
BBU	BaseBand Unit
C-RAN	Cloud Radio Access Network
cMTC	Critical Machine-Type Communications
CO	Central Offices
CPRI	Common Public Radio Interface
DC2DC	Datacenter-to-Datacenter
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile BroadBand
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
IoT	Internet of Things
MIMO	Multi-Input Multi-Output
mMTC	Massive Machine-Type Communications
Multi-RAT	Multiple Radio Access Technologies
OBSAI	Open Base Station Architecture Initiative
OLT	Optical Line Terminals
RAN	Radio Access Network
RRH	Remote Radio Head
SDM	Spatial Division Multiplexing
SIPTO	Selected IP Traffic Offload
SSON	Spectrum Switched Optical Networks
UDN	Ultra-Dense Networks
VoLTE	Voice over LTE
WSON	Wavelength Switched Optical Networks

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